

Polytropes and Optimization

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Introduction

The goal of this thesis is to introduce tropical convexity and explore structural results of polytropes with an outlook to combinatorial optimization. We work in the tropical semiring $\mathbb{T} = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, \oplus, \odot)$ where \oplus is the minimum and \odot is addition in the usual sense. Tropical convexity is roughly a formalization of the idea of 'piece wise linear convexity'. We say a set A is *tropically convex* if for all points a and b in A the *tropical convex combination*

$$\lambda \odot a \oplus \mu \odot b \quad \lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{T}$$

is contained in A . Tropically convex sets have the linear space $\mathbb{R} \cdot (1, \dots, 1) = \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1}$ in their lineality space, where $\mathbb{1} = (1, \dots, 1)$ is the all ones vector. Thus, we say they live in the *tropical torus* $\mathbb{R}^d / \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1} = \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. We can define a *tropical convex hull* analogously to the case of ordinary convexity. For a finite point configuration V in the tropical torus we define a *tropical polytope* as the tropical convex hull of V .

Tropical polytopes have been studied from various perspectives in the literature. Roughly, these are combinatorial, graphical, and algebraic. While these perspectives give us a lot of structure to work with, it can be difficult to find information on how to move from one point of view to another. One of our aims is to understand the different views on tropical convexity and see how they fit together.

As we will see, tropical polytopes are quite different from polytopes coming from ordinary convexity. Nevertheless, a tropical polytope can sometimes also be convex in the ordinary sense. We call such a tropical polytope a *polytrope*. While having all the structure mentioned above, polytropes also allow one to use tools from ordinary polyhedral geometry.

We begin in section 1 by introducing foundational facts about tropical geometry. We then formalize the idea of tropical convexity and compare it to ordinary convexity. This leads us to the definition of a polytrope. We recall the Cayley trick from polyhedral geometry, as it will play a significant part later on. With the theory of tropical polynomials and their vanishing sets, we explore tropical hyperplanes and their arrangements. This sets the scene for the algebraic perspective on tropical convexity.

In section 2, we introduce a class of polyhedra called *weighted digraph polyhedra*, which were defined in [JL16]. These polyhedra bring in the graph theoretic perspective on tropical convexity. The inequalities come from the arcs of a digraph on the node set $[d] = \{1, \dots, d\}$. For a weighted digraph Γ with an arc (i, j) , where i and j are in $[d]$, we associate the inequality

$$x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij}, \tag{1}$$

where w_{ij} is the weight of the arc (i, j) . Inequalities of this type appear in combinatorial optimization in dual flow problems. The problem is usually to find a so-called *feasible potential* for the nodes of the digraph Γ . With this in mind, we would like better to describe the vertices of the solution spaces of these problems. In this section we rewrite the proofs of Lemmas 2 and 3, 22, and 23 in [JL16] in Lemmas 35, 39, and 44 respectively. We do this as we will use the arguments in subsection 4.1 to prove a structural result.

As mentioned above, one reason that tropical convexity is interesting is because it can be seen from different perspectives. Section 3 tells the story of how one can move between these different perspectives. There, three constructions derived from a finite point configuration V in the tropical torus are discussed. Some proofs found in the literature are rewritten to improve clarity. This includes the proof of Theorem 1 of [DS04] (for us Theorem 46) and some of the machinery leading up to it. This theorem is referred to as the "Structural Theorem of Tropical Convexity" in [JL16]. Section 2 provides background for subsection 3.2, and subsection 1.5 provides the background for subsection 3.3.

In sections 4 and 5, we discuss our contributions. Our aim is to better understand the structure of polytropes and specifically their vertices. We focus on the vertices since the dual flow problems discussed above have polytrope solution spaces. When our solution space is a polytrope P , we have from ordinary polyhedral geometry the description of P 's vertices by spanning trees. These spanning trees come from the weighted digraph that described P as a weighted digraph polyhedron. In subsection 4.1 we compare these spanning trees with descriptions of the vertices coming from viewing P as a tropical polytope. We prove Proposition 71, stated below, which highlights this connection.

Proposition. *Consider a polytrope $P = Q(W^*) = \text{tconv}(V) \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, with vertices $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$. For a face F of P , let $B_F \subset B(V)$ be the covector graph of F and let $\bar{\Gamma}_F \subset \Gamma(W^*)$ be the union subgraph of F . Then we have*

$$(i, j') \in B_F \quad \text{if and only if} \quad (i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F.$$

In words, this proposition proves a connection between the two graphical descriptions of faces of a polytrope. One comes from the weighted digraph, in other words the inequality description from classical polyhedral geometry. The other comes from the covector graph describing a cell in the covector decomposition, in other words from tropical convexity theory.

In subsection 4.2, we discuss some potential structural results about polytropes (see Question 74) and give motivating examples. The potential results are promising as we have tested them against some large examples, this is in subsection 5.2.

Subsection 5.1 explains how many of the figures in this thesis were generated. We explain how to use the software OSCAR and the polymake library within it. In subsection 5.2, we spell out how to do some computations in tropical convexity using OSCAR. Tropical convexity is a relatively young field and the mathematical software is still catching up. Some of the computations we were interested in were not yet possible in OSCAR. We show some functions that filled these gaps, which have been merged into the code base of OSCAR. We also include computational experiments that test a potential structural result mentioned in subsection 4.2. This subsection contains joint work with Kamillo Ferry, Dante Luber, and Lena Weis.

In section 6, we explain a potential application of structural results about polytropes to the optimization of periodic timetabling in public transport. These are an example of the dual flow problems mentioned above. We pose some possible next steps that may be helpful in an optimization context. These steps are motivated by examples in 4.2.

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Literature Review

Tropical geometry is a relatively new field that has deep connections to algebraic geometry and combinatorics. While the connections to algebraic geometry are very rich, we do not explore them here. We focus on tropical geometry as a geometry over the tropical semiring $\mathbb{T} = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, \oplus, \odot)$. Tropical geometry has deep connections to combinatorial optimization and linear programming. Initial connections between linear programming and a max-plus algebra were made in [BA09]. The main approaches to solving linear programs are the simplex algorithm and interior point methods.

The simplex algorithm was tropicalized in [ABGJ14a] and then connected to mean payoff games in [ABGJ15]. Complexity results about mean payoff games then gave complexity results about the tropicalized simplex algorithm. The PhD thesis of Pascal Benchimol [Ben14] gives an overview/introduction to this line of research.

Tropical geometry was used in [ABGJ18] and its follow up [ABGJ21] to show that a class (log-barrier) of interior point methods is not strongly polynomial. The main development was the tropical central path, which made use of the difficult example defined as a long and winding path in [ABGJ14b]. The authors of [AGV22] then generalized this result to a larger class of interior point methods (self-concordant barrier). Similar results are shown in [ZLY24] for a different class (short-step) of interior point methods. The tropicalization of the entropic barrier (an example of a self-concordant barrier with some more assumptions) central path is studied in [AAGH20].

In [Loh20], tropical linear programming is introduced in its own right. This is in contrast to the work mentioned above, which looked at the interplay between classical linear programming and tropical linear programming. The goal in [Loh20] is to solve a tropical inequality system, where the inequalities are of the form

$$\min \{\lambda_i + x_i \mid i \in I\} \leq \min \{\lambda_l + x_l \mid l \in [d] \setminus I\},$$

where $\lambda_i \in \mathbb{T}$ are elements of the tropical semiring. The algorithm developed there uses a new combinatorial structure: a signed tropical matroid.

The next step in optimization after linear programming is semidefinite programming, see [BPT13]. Here the spectrahedron is central. A tropical geometric point of view was established in [AGS18] and [AGKS18] with connections to stochastic mean payoff games. This was expanded on in [AGS20]. For an overview see the PhD thesis of Mateusz Skomra [Sko18].

There are optimization problems where we have competing choices for objective functions. Here, we try to find solutions which are locally optimal. These local optima are called Pareto optima. In [JL20], tropical convex hull computations are used in an algorithm that solved these types of problems.

The tropical convex hull mentioned above fits into the wider theory of tropical convexity. The first steps in tropical convexity were in the context of idempotent semimodules in [LMS01] and [CGQ04]. The theory took its first shape in the paper [DS04]. Since then more perspectives have been developed. These perspectives include: combinatorial, graph theoretic, polyhedral, and algebraic. Tropical convexity fits into the larger world of tropical geometry, which has many deep connections to algebraic geometry, via a field with a non trivial valuation. A common example is the field of Puiseux series with the valuation as the degree map. While we will need one or two results from the algebraic geometric side of tropical geometry, we mostly stay on the combinatorial side.

Tropical convexity has been particularly successful in its applicability. We mention applications that appear in the literature. Starting at the seminal paper [DS04], a connection with phylogenetic trees from the field of bioinformatics was made. The authors of [JSY07] make connections between tropical convexity and affine buildings with an application to biology in mind. For recent work on this connection see [CC23], where the authors make a connection to the Fermat-Weber optimization problem.

Through cellular resolutions of polytopes, tropical geometry has a strong connection to commutative algebra. This is investigated in [JK10], where the main result, which we state in Theorem 14, is shown to be equivalent to whether the Segre product of two full polynomial rings has the Gorenstein property. In [ADS22], the polyhedral decompositions that arise in tropical convexity are used to study monomial and binomial ideals. More specifically, new formulas of homological invariants of toric edge ideals of bipartite graphs are found using this tropical perspective.

The faces and outer descriptions of tropical polyhedra have proven to be difficult to understand. Another seminal paper in tropical convexity is [Jos05], which begins to tackle this problem. In [DY07] the authors refine the definitions; however this is still a work in progress. In [LS23], the authors find that the search of the right description of the faces of tropical polyhedra is a deep question that branches out to monomial ideals in commutative algebra and order theory. Work in this area is ongoing, for example on the f -conjecture in [Spe08]

In the soon to be released preprint [AF24], the graph theoretic side of tropical convexity is used in connection with graphical statistical modelling. This is work in algebraic statistics.

Since there are no additive inverses in the tropical semiring $\mathbb{T}_{\min} = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, \oplus, \odot)$ tropical hyperplanes behave somewhat like ordinary hyperplanes that have been intersected with the nonnegative real orthant $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^d$. An example of this is that three tropical lines that are not parallel (whatever that means for now) may have non empty intersection. In [LV20] and later in [LS24], there are attempts to resolve this and other drawbacks of tropical convexity. A large part of the fix is to introduce signed tropical numbers. In [LS24], the authors also show connections and applications to matroids over hyperfields.

Hyperplanes are central in ordinary convexity. Analogously, tropical hyperplanes are central in tropical convexity. We will see that tropical hyperplane arrangements give an approach to constructing tropical convexity. Tropical hyperplane arrangements, like ordinary hyperplane

arrangements, have connections to matroid theory. In [AD09], a tropical version of oriented matroids is defined and used to study tropical hyperplane arrangements. In [FR15], a special type of tropical linear spaces defined by a point configuration V are shown to have dual properties with the tropical hyperplane arrangement of V . There the tropical Grassmannian is central, see [SS04].

The so called "Fundamental Structural Theorem of Tropical Convexity", shown in [DS04], connects point configurations in the tropical torus to triangulations of products of simplices. This allows one to use subdivisions and polyhedral geometry to tackle problems in tropical convexity. This is done in [CLY24] to extend ideas in tropical convexity beyond the tropical world.

The central objects of study in this thesis are polytropes, which are tropical polytopes that are also convex in the ordinary sense. Polytropes are also studied outside of the tropical context. There they have been called *Alcoved polytopes of type 'A'* in [LP07] and [LP18] and are studied as polytopes arising from affine Coxeter arrangements.

The various structures built into the definition of a polytrope provide many tools with which one can study them. In [Tra17], one can find algorithms to enumerate combinatorial types of polytropes. In [JL16], the graph theoretical side of tropical convexity is constructed. The authors of [JK15] spell out what polytropes look like from this perspective.

In public transport optimization, the timetable that the system operates on is of great significance. The standard model used for solving for a periodic timetable is the *Periodic Event Scheduling Problem* (PESP). This was first introduced in [SU89]. There are many approaches to solving the PESP. The most fruitful approach has been to formulate the PESP as a mixed integer program. The inequalities there are of the form in (1). This prompted work that used weighted digraph polyhedra, specifically polytropes, to the formulate the solution space of timetables. This connection is made in [BLM22a], which also contains a quick introduction to the PESP. In [BLM22b], this connection was used to develop a heuristic called the tropical neighbourhood search. We expand on this in subsection 6.1.

1 The Tropical Setting, Convexity, and Subdivisions

Tropical geometry is a new field with connections to algebraic geometry and combinatorics. We introduce the basics of tropical geometry with a focus on the combinatorial side. Part of this combinatorial side is the theory of tropical convexity, which will be the main focus of this thesis. We introduce tropical convexity in subsection 1.2 and contrast it with ordinary convexity. In subsection 1.3 we introduce our main objects of interest, *polytropes*, which are the outcome of the combination of tropical and ordinary convexity. For further sections we will need to review some concepts from polyhedral geometry, such as subdivisions and the Cayley Trick. We do this in subsection 1.4. The Cayley trick will be useful to make connections between different perspectives of tropical convexity, specifically in subsection 3.3, which describes tropical convexity through tropical hyperplane arrangements. We introduce the background of tropical hyperplane arrangements needed in subsection 1.5.

1.1 The Tropical Setting

The *tropical semiring* is the triple $(\mathbb{T}, \oplus, \odot)$ where $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ and where \oplus is minimum and \odot is usual addition. For $x, y \in \mathbb{T}$, we have

$$x \oplus y := \min\{x, y\} \quad x \odot y := x + y.$$

Some examples:

$$2 \oplus 3 = 2 \quad 2 \odot 3 = 5 \quad 2 \oplus \infty = 2 \quad 3 \odot \infty = \infty.$$

One can also work with maximum instead of minimum, in that case we write $\mathbb{T}_{\max} = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\}, \boxplus, \odot)$.

We can extend this and define the *tropical semimodule* as the triple $(\mathbb{T}^n, \oplus, \odot)$. For $a, b \in \mathbb{T}^n$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{T}$, we have vector addition \oplus and scalar multiplication \odot defined as follows:

$$\oplus : \mathbb{T}^n \times \mathbb{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^n, \quad (a, b) \mapsto a \oplus b := \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \end{pmatrix} \oplus \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ \vdots \\ b_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \oplus b_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \oplus b_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \min\{a_1, b_1\} \\ \vdots \\ \min\{a_n, b_n\} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\odot : \mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^n, \quad (\lambda, a) \mapsto \lambda \odot a := \begin{pmatrix} \lambda \odot a_1 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda \odot a_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda + a_1 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda + a_n \end{pmatrix} = \lambda \mathbb{1} + a,$$

where $\mathbb{1}^T = (1, \dots, 1)$ is the all ones vector. We define tropical matrix multiplication in the same way as usual matrix multiplication but with the tropical operations in the place of the usual ones. For matrices $A \in \mathbb{T}^{n \times d}$ and $B \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times m}$ with entries as tropical numbers, we have

$$A \odot B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1d} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & \dots & a_{nd} \end{pmatrix} \odot \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & \dots & b_{1m} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ b_{d1} & \dots & b_{dm} \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow (A \odot B)_{ij} = \bigoplus_{k=1}^d a_{ik} \odot b_{kj}.$$

Tropical arithmetic allows us to define *tropical polynomials* and the semiring that they live in, $\mathbb{T}[x_1, \dots, x_d]$. It will be convenient for us to think of polynomials as maps from \mathbb{N}^d to \mathbb{T} . Here $u \in \mathbb{N}$ represents the degree vector of a monomial. The element of the tropical semiring $a_u \in \mathbb{T}$ that u gets mapped to, is the monomial's coefficient. For f to be a polynomial it must have a finite number of terms. Thinking of f as a map, we say that the complement of the preimage of $\infty \in \mathbb{T}$ has finite cardinality, in symbols

$$\#(\mathbb{N}^d \setminus f^{-1}(\infty)) = M, \quad M \in \mathbb{N}.$$

We call this finite subset of \mathbb{N}^d the support of f , denoted $\text{supp}(f)$. With the above notation f would have M terms and $\text{supp}(f)$ would have M points. Thus tropical polynomials are of the form

$$\bigoplus_{u \in \text{supp}(f) \subset \mathbb{N}^d} a_u \odot x_1^{\odot u_1} \odot \dots \odot x_d^{\odot u_d}.$$

Example 1. We have an example of a tropical polynomial in the polynomial semiring $\mathbb{T}[x]$. Note that since the coefficient of the x^4 term is ∞ this polynomial is a cubic. We usually do not write terms with ∞ as a coefficient. We drop the x^4 term when writing f in usual arithmetic.

$$\begin{aligned} f &= \infty \odot x^{\odot 4} \oplus 5 \odot x^{\odot 3} \oplus 3 \odot x^{\odot 2} \oplus 2 \odot x \oplus 3 \\ &= \min\{5 + 3x, 3 + 2x, 2 + x, 3\}. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: The graph of f with its vanishing set marked in its domain. The shaded region along with the upper boundary form the dome of f , $\mathcal{D}(f)$.

We say a tropical polynomial f *vanishes* at a point, a , if the minimum is attained by two or more terms of the polynomial. We denote the vanishing set of a tropical polynomial as $\mathcal{T}(f)$, which is called the *tropical hypersurface of f* . $\mathcal{T}(f)$ arises naturally when we look at the graph of a tropical polynomial. We define the *dome* of a d -variate polynomial f as the unbounded polyhedron,

$$\mathcal{D}(f) = \{(x_1, \dots, x_d, y) \in \mathbb{R}^{(d+1)} \mid y \leq f(x_1, \dots, x_d)\}.$$

The name comes from the fact that when we take \oplus to be \min , we will have a concave down graph made up of piecewise linear segments. Between these segments are breakpoints where

the minimum is attained by more than one term. Thus we can give another definition of the the tropical hypersurface using the co dimension one skeleton of the boundary of the dome,

$$\mathcal{T}(f) = \pi_{d+1}\left((\partial\mathcal{D}(f))^1\right),$$

where π_{d+1} is the projection onto \mathbb{R}^d (the $d + 1^{th}$ coordinate is killed) and $(\cdot)^1$ denotes taking the co dimension one skeleton. Note that the tropical hypersurface of a d -variate tropical polynomial gives a polyhedral subdivision of \mathbb{R}^d . In this subdivision the maximal dimensional cells are where the minimum is attained by just one monomial, these maximal dimensional cells are referred to as *regions*. In Figure 1 we see the dome of the polynomial introduced in Example 1, with $\mathcal{T}(f)$ marked in red.

We define the *Newton polytope*, $\mathcal{N}(f) = \text{conv}\{a \in \text{supp}(f)\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, the support terminology comes from viewing f as a function from \mathbb{N}^d to \mathbb{T} , as mentioned above. If we see the coefficients of f as a height function on the lattice points in $\text{supp}(f)$ we get a regular subdivision of $\mathcal{N}(f)$. We refer to this as the *dual subdivision* of f , denoted $\mathcal{S}(f)$. See section 1.4 for definitions of and more about subdivisions. The following theorem gives a connection between the polyhedral subdivision induced by the tropical hypersurface $\mathcal{T}(f)$ of a polynomial and its dual subdivision $\mathcal{S}(f)$. It is the reason behind the use of the name "dual".

Theorem 2. (Theorem 1.13, [Jos21]) *For a tropical polynomial f in d variables, there is an antiisomorphism between the face posets of the subdivisions $\mathcal{T}(f)$ and $\mathcal{S}(f)$. From this antiisomorphism we have a bijection between the k -dimensional cells of the tropical hypersurface $\mathcal{T}(f)$ and the $(d - k)$ -dimensional cells of $\mathcal{S}(f)$ for $0 \leq k \leq d - 1$. The regions of $\mathcal{T}(f)$ correspond to the vertices of $\mathcal{S}(f)$.*

Example 3. Below we have a tropical polynomial f in the polynomial semiring $\mathbb{T}[x, y]$. In Figure 2 we see its tropical hypersurface $\mathcal{T}(f)$ and the dual subdivision $\mathcal{S}(f)$ of its Newton polytope $\mathcal{N}(f)$.

$$\begin{aligned} f &= 7 \odot x^3 \oplus 10 \odot x^3 y \oplus 2 \odot x^3 y^2 \oplus 8 \odot x^3 y^3 \oplus 1 \odot x^2 y \oplus 1 \odot x^2 y^2 \\ &\quad \oplus 1 \odot x^2 y^3 \oplus xy \oplus 1 \odot xy^2 \oplus 3 \odot xy^3 \oplus 0 \oplus y \oplus 2 \odot y^2 \oplus 4 \odot y^3 \\ &= \min\{7 + 3x, 10 + 3x + y, 2 + 3x + 2y, 8 + 3x + 3y, 1 + 2x + y, \\ &\quad 1 + 2x + 2y, 1 + 2x + 3y, 0 + x + y, 1 + x + 2y, 3 + x + 3y, \\ &\quad 0, 0 + y, 2 + 2y, 4 + 3y\}. \end{aligned}$$

The *tropical torus* or *tropical affine space* $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ is the set $\mathbb{R}^d / \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1}$, which we usually identify with $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ via the homeomorphism

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)} &= \mathbb{R}^d / \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(d-1)} \\ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) + \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1} &= (0, x_2 - x_1, \dots, x_d - x_1) + \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1} \longmapsto (x_2 - x_1, \dots, x_d - x_1). \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Tropical geometry is concerned mostly with polyhedral objects. The tropical torus is a natural space to work in as many objects in tropical geometry have the linear space $\mathbb{R}(1, \dots, 1) = \mathbb{R}\mathbb{1}$ in their lineality space, here $\mathbb{1} = (1, \dots, 1)$ is the all ones vectors. Throughout this thesis we

Figure 2: Vertices on the right correspond with regions on the left.

have examples drawn in $\mathbb{R}^d \cong \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^d$, $d = 2, 3$. Another space of interest, which mimics the compactness of classical projective space is *tropical projective space*. It is defined as

$$\mathbb{TP}^{d-1} = (\mathbb{T}^d \setminus \{\infty\})/\mathbb{R}\mathbb{1},$$

where $\infty = (\infty, \dots, \infty)$ is the all ∞ 's vector in \mathbb{T}^d .

In order to study tropical convexity we will need a central object, the tropical hyperplane. Define *tropical hyperplanes* as the vanishing set of a linear homogeneous tropical polynomial

$$f(x) = a_1 \odot x_1 \oplus \dots \oplus a_d \odot x_d. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathcal{T}(f)$ will be the positive coordinate axes in \mathbb{R}^d shifted by $-a$ with lineality space $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{1}$ since all monomials are degree one. We say a is the *apex* of the hyperplane. This allows us to define *tropical halfspaces*, which are not quite "half". For a tropical hyperplane H_a with apex a , dividing its complement inside $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ gives us d connected components called *open sectors*.

A *sector* is the topological closure of an open sector. Thus, for $j \in [d]$ the j^{th} sector of a hyperplane with apex a is given by,

$$\mathcal{S}_j(a) = \left\{ (x_1, \dots, x_d) \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)} \mid \min_{k \in [d]} (x_k - a_k) = x_j - a_j \right\}. \quad (4)$$

Write $\mathcal{S}_I := \bigcup \{\bar{\mathcal{S}}_i \mid i \in I\}$ for any set $I \subset \{0, \dots, d\}$. For each $I \subset \{0, 1, \dots, d\}$ with $1 \leq \#I \leq d$ the set $-a + \mathcal{S}_I$ is the *closed tropical halfspace of H_a of type I* . Note that this definition of a sector is for the min tropical numbers. For a *max sector* we change the min in (4) to a max.

Remark 4. There are d terms in the minimum in (4). Since each term will attain the minimum uniquely for some points, we have that a tropical hyperplane defines d sectors. These sectors can be ordered with the same ordering as the coordinates that attain the minimum in them.

Tropical halfspaces and their connection to tropical convexity (section 1.2) are treated thoroughly in [Jos05], which we will draw results from later.

Example 5.

$$f(x) = a_1 \odot x_1 \oplus a_2 \odot x_2 \oplus a_3 \odot x_3, \text{ with } a_i \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Take the hyperplane H_a with apex $a \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Then below we have examples of two types of tropical halfspaces based off of the same hyperplane. In Figure 3, the red halfspace is written as $-a + S_{1,2}$ and the blue halfspace is written as $-a + S_3$.

(a) $\mathcal{T}(f)$ viewed in $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{TA}^2$. The sectors are numbered like in (4)

(b) Two tropical halfspaces, the union of which cover the tropical torus \mathbb{TA}^2 .

Figure 3: Tropical Hyperplane and Tropical Halfspace

Remark 6. As mentioned in the introduction tropical geometry has another side closely connected to algebraic geometry. Algebraic varieties over an algebraically closed field K with a non trivial evaluation have a deep connection with tropical hypersurfaces. Set V to be an algebraic variety coming from an ideal I . The 'Fundamental Theorem of Tropical Algebraic Geometry' equates the image of V under the valuation map of K and the tropical hypersurfaces that come from tropicalizing the polynomials in I . A few results we need use this side of tropical geometry in their proof. However since this is largely outside the scope of this thesis we omit it. The interested reader can see section 3 of [MS15] or section 2 of [Jos21].

1.2 Tropical Convexity

Tropical convexity is the tropicalization of ordinary convexity. This brings us to building a theory of piecewise convexity. We first recall ordinary or classical convexity, in order to contrast it with its tropical counterpart. We say a set A is convex if it contains the *convex combination* of any two points $x, y \in A$

$$\lambda x + \mu y \in A \quad \text{for all } \lambda, \mu \geq 0 \quad \text{such that } \lambda + \mu = 1.$$

One can show that a set A is convex if and only if it is equal to its convex hull $\text{conv}(A)$, where

$$\text{conv}(A) = \left\{ \lambda_1 x_1 + \cdots + \lambda_n x_n \mid x_i \in A, \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1, \lambda_i \geq 0 \right\}.$$

If $A = V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ then $\text{conv}(V)$ is called a *polytope*. We assume the reader has basic knowledge of polyhedral geometry. See [Gr03] for a reference.

We say a subset $A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ is tropically convex if for any two points $x, y \in A$ the *tropical convex combination*

$$\lambda \odot x \oplus \mu \odot y,$$

is in A for all $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{T}$. Note that we do not mention λ and μ being nonnegative, this is since there are no additives inverses in the tropical semiring. By the definition it is easy to see that any tropically convex set will contain the lineality space $\mathbb{R}\mathbf{1}$. For that reason we always look at tropically convex sets in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. Now like in the ordinary convexity case we define the *tropical convex hull* of a set A as

$$\text{tconv}(A) = \{\lambda_1 \odot x_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \lambda_n \odot x_n \mid \lambda_i \in \mathbb{R}\}.$$

and note that A is tropically convex if and only if it is equal to its tropical convex hull. Also note that the tropical convex hull is not purely the tropicalization of the ordinary convex hull (it is, in fact, the tropicalization of the ordinary conic hull).

Analogously to the ordinary case, for $A = V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, we say $P = \text{tconv}(V)$ is a *tropical polytope* with its set of *tropical vertices* V . These will be the central objects of study in this thesis.

Tropical and ordinary convexity share similar properties. We recall the following result from [DS04] to show this. We include the proof of the last statement, since it will be relevant to us later.

Theorem 7. (Theorem 2, [DS04]) *Let P and Q be arbitrary tropically convex sets, then*

- (i) *The intersection of P and Q , viewed in \mathbb{R}^d or in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ is tropically convex.*
- (ii) *The projection of P onto a coordinate hyperplane is tropically convex.*
- (iii) *P is a contractible space.*
- (iv) *The Cartesian product, $P \times Q$ is tropically convex.*
- (v) *The ordinary hyperplane $\{x_i - x_j = w\}$, for $w \in \mathbb{R}$ is tropically convex.*

Proof. (of (v)) Take u and v in $H = \{x_i - x_j = w\}$, then $u_i - u_j = v_i - v_j$ and $u_i - v_i = u_j - v_j$. To show H is tropically convex it is enough to show the tropical convex combination of u and v is in H . In other words, for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$(a \odot u \oplus b \odot v)_i - (a \odot u \oplus b \odot v)_j = w.$$

Since this holds in all cases, the tropical line between u and v is inside H . □

See Example 9 below for a demonstration of the following result, which describes what tropical line segments look like.

Proposition 8. (Proposition 3, [DS04]) *The tropical line segment between two points x and y in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ viewed in $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ is the concatenation of at most $d - 1$ ordinary line segments. The slope of each of these line segments is a zero-one vector (a vector with only 0 and 1 as entries).*

Proof Sketch. Reordering the coordinates so that $y_1 - x_1 \leq \dots \leq y_d - x_d$ allows us to order the 'break points' of the tropical line segment. Compute

$$(y_i - x_i) \odot x \oplus y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_i, y_i - x_i + x_{i+1}, \dots, y_i - x_i + x_d).$$

Here setting $i = 0, d$ gives x and y respectively and the $2 \leq i \leq n - 1$ give the break points that the $d - 1$ line segments connect. \square

The following examples give the reader some intuition of what tropical convexity looks like and how it is different from ordinary convexity. We start with line segments.

Example 9. In Figure 4 we see the tropical convex hulls of the point configurations

$$V_1 = \{(0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 0)\} \quad \text{and} \quad V_2 = \{(0, -1, -1), (0, 1, 0)\},$$

which are subsets of $\mathbb{TA}^2 \cong \mathbb{R}^2$. To contrast we also have the ordinary convex hull of

$$V_O = \{(0, 1), (1, 0)\} \subset \mathbb{R}^2.$$

The yellow points mark the points in the set we are taking the tropical hull of. We refer to the red points as the *break points* of a tropical line segment.

Figure 4: Note that Figures (b) and (c) show that tropical convex hulls are not necessarily convex.

It is important to see how tropical polytopes and ordinary polytopes differ and how they are truly different notions. In Figure 5(a) below, we see an example of a polytope that is tropically convex which is not a tropical polytope. Two tropical line segments are marked to show that we cannot get the orange triangle by taking the tropical convex hull of a finite number of points in it.

Likewise in Figure 5(b) we see a tropical polytope (specifically a tropical triangle) that is not ordinarily convex. For a tropical polytope $t\text{conv}(V) = P$, we refer to the minimal set of points V' needed to get P as their tropical convex hull as the *tropical vertices* of P (in our figures we mark these with yellow points). The notion of a minimal set is made clearer below in Proposition 10. We refer to the vertices of the polytope seen in $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ as the *pseudoverties* of P . In particular, the tropical vertices are an (often strict) subset of the pseudoverties.

Figure 5

Tropical polytopes can be thought of as polytopal complexes, with different dimensional cells. Figures 6 and 7 show some different ways a tropical polytope can look. As above the yellow points mark the tropical vertices and the red points appear as break points, or as *non-tropical pseudoverties*.

Figure 6: Two dimensional tropical polytopes

The following result is the tropical version of Carathéodory's Theorem and gives us a notion of a minimal generating set of tropical vertices for a tropical polytope.

Proposition 10. ([DS04], Proposition 5) *If x is in the tropical convex hull of n points in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, then x is in the tropical convex hull of d of them.*

Hyperplanes and the halfspaces they define are central to the study of ordinary polytopes. For tropical polytopes the story is more complicated. We list a few results towards an exterior description of tropical polytopes to give the reader a view on this side of tropical convexity. Exterior descriptions of tropical polytopes are still not fully understood and there is ongoing work on the subject.

Figure 7: Three dimensional tropical polytope and its 'exploded' view showing all of its cells.

Proposition 11. *For tropical hyperplane and tropical halfspaces as defined in subsection 1.1, we have*

1. ([DS04], Propostion 6) *Tropical hyperplanes are tropically convex.*
2. ([Jos05], Propositon 2.17) *Tropical halfspaces are tropically convex.*
3. ([Jos05], Theorem 3.6) *Tropical polytopes are bounded intersections of finitely many tropical halfspaces.*

1.3 Polytropes

In the previous subsection we discussed tropical convexity and tropical polytopes, which are defined as the tropical convex hull of a finite set of points. We now combine tropical and ordinary convexity. The product of this combination is *polytropes*, which are tropical polytopes that are also convex in the ordinary sense. Polytropes have a lot of nice structure, which we will introduce here and expand on in subsection 3.4 once we know more about tropical convexity. We will later see that polytropes are the building blocks of tropical polytopes.

We say a set is *convex in the ordinary sense* in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ if its image in $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ under the homeomorphism described in (2) is convex.

Definition 12. *A polytrope P is a tropical polytope,*

$$P = \text{tconv}(V), \quad \text{where } V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}.$$

that is also convex in the ordinary sense. A polytrope may have ordinary vertices that are not tropical vertices. We refer to the set of all the ordinary vertices of P (tropical or not) as its *pseudoverties*.

A tropical polytope in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ is a *tropical $(d-1)$ simplex* if it is the tropical convex hull of d points which do not lie in the boundary of a tropical halfspace. Note that a tropical simplex is not necessarily a polytrope, see Figure 5(b) for an example.

Remark 13. The standard simplex, Δ_{d-1} comes from taking the convex hull of the standard basis $\{e_j\}_{j=1}^d$ of \mathbb{R}^d . We say the points in \mathbb{R}^d (that are described by the standard basis vectors) are in *general position* or *generic position* as the corresponding vectors span \mathbb{R}^d . Another way of saying this is the determinant of the matrix formed by the vectors as rows is not singular. In the case of the standard basis this is $\det(I) \neq 0$, where I is the identity matrix. So we say that the vertices of a simplex are always in general position.

In subsection 1.5 we make precise what it means for a point configuration to be in general position in a tropical context. But for now we note that in the tropical world the vertices of a tropical simplex do not have to be in tropical generic position.

Theorem 14. (Theorem 12, [JK10]) *A polytrope is a tropical simplex.*

The proof of this result uses Puiseux series to categorize intersections of tropical halfspaces, this is used along with the action of S_n on sectors making up tropical halfspaces to show that only single sector tropical halfspaces can maintain ordinary convexity. Then there is an upper bound on how many tropical vertices can exist. For details see sections 2 and 3 in [JK10].

Example 15. Polytopes can look quite different even while coming from the same number of tropical vertices. Below in Figures 8 and 9 we show examples in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ for $d = 3, 4$. In [Tra17] polytopes in some low dimensions are categorized. The notion of genericness mentioned in the captions of the figures is explained in subsection 1.5.

Figure 8: Polytopes in \mathbb{TA}^2 . As mentioned Remark 13 we have that only the polytrope in Figure (a) is generic. This is made precise in subsection 1.5.

Figure 9: Polytopes in \mathbb{TA}^3

1.4 The Cayley Trick

Before we continue to our main topic, we take a small detour through polyhedral subdivisions. We introduce the Cayley trick and mention its connection to regular subdivisions of the product of simplices. We follow the exposition of [San05]. A detailed non trivial example with many figures can be found in [DLRS10]. First we recall some elementary definitions.

First, for a polytope P , a *subpolytope* of P is a convex hull of a subset of the vertices of P . A face of P is a subpolytope, but not all subpolytopes are faces.

Definition 16. A *polyhedral subdivision* S of a finite set of points $A \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ or its associated polytope $\text{conv}(A)$ is a collection of polyhedra called *cells* such that

1. The union of the cells of S covers $\text{conv}(A)$
2. The intersection of two cells is a proper face of both cells
3. For any cell in S all its faces are also cells of S

We usually omit the word 'polyhedral'. Subdivisions form a poset under *refinement*. A subdivision S *refines* a subdivision T if for each

$$K \in S \text{ there is an } L \in T, \text{ such that } K \subset L. \quad (5)$$

In this case we write $S \leq T$. The minimal elements of this poset, where all cells are simplices, are called *triangulations*. The unique maximal element of the subdivision poset is the trivial subdivision, where there is one cell equal to the whole space. We also sometimes say T is *coarser* than S if $S \leq T$, or that S is *finer*.

Define the *Minkowski sum* of n sets in \mathbb{R}^d , $\{L_1, \dots, L_n\}$ as

$$L_1 + \dots + L_n = \sum_{i=1}^n L_i = \{x_1 + \dots + x_n \mid x_i \in L_i\} \subset \mathbb{R}^d.$$

It is a simple observation that the Minkowski sum of polytopes is a polytope.

Definition 17. A *regular subdivision*, as mentioned in Theorem 2, comes from assigning the set of points A a height function $h : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and then looking at the polyhedron coming from the convex hull of the raised points plus an upwards ray. The 'downward' projection of the lower faces of this polyhedron gives a subdivision of $\text{conv}(A)$. More precisely we set $P = \text{conv}(A) \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and define, using the Minkowski sum,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P} &= \{(0, \dots, 0, \lambda) \mid \lambda \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}\} + \text{conv}(\{(a, h(a)) \mid a \in A\}) \subset \mathbb{R}^{(d+1)} \\ &= \{(p, \lambda) \mid p \in P, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}\}. \end{aligned}$$

We label the lower faces of \tilde{P} as $\{\tilde{K}_1, \dots, \tilde{K}_l\}$. We look at the projection $\pi_{d+1} : \mathbb{R}^{(d+1)} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, which kills the last coordinate. Then the images of the lower faces $\pi_{d+1}(\tilde{K}_i)$ give a subdivision of P . Any subdivision arising this way is called regular.

Figure 10: Regular subdivision of a one dimensional polytope.

Definition 18. We fix an ordered set of polytopes $P_1, \dots, P_n \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, and denote $\sum_i P_i = P$ as the Minkowski sum of the P_i 's. Although P is a polytope in its own right, we still think of it as the n -tuple (P_1, \dots, P_n) . Define a *Minkowski cell* of P , as any full dimensional cell of P that comes from the Minkowski sum of subpolytopes of the P_i 's, (which are not necessarily full dimensional). A *mixed subdivision* S of P is a subdivision such that all the cells are Minkowski cells, that also respects the following property: for each B and C in S , where

$$B = \sum_i B_i \text{ and } C = \sum_i C_i \quad B_i, C_i \subset P_i.$$

We have that $B_i \cap C_i$ is a face of both.

There is an assumption built into this definition, which is that we fix the Minkowski decomposition of P . This is why it is important to think of P not just as a polytope, but really as an ordered n -tuple of polytopes. Note that, by this definition, two Minkowski cells that form the same subset of P that come from different Minkowski sums are considered different. One way

to think of a mixed subdivision is a subdivision where each cell has a label telling us a unique Minkowski decomposition of itself, and such that the labels of intersecting cells are somehow 'compatible'.

With a link to regular subdivisions in mind, we describe a procedure that defines a special type of mixed subdivision. Fix a polytope P with Minkowski decomposition $P_1, \dots, P_n \subset \mathbb{R}^d$. We assign to every $P_i \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ in the fixed Minkowski decomposition of P a height function h_i that assigns to each vertex of P_i a real number. Denote the lifted polytope by \tilde{P}_i . We now look at the Minkowski sum $\bar{P} = \sum_i \tilde{P}_i$, which is different from \tilde{P} above. Like we did with regular subdivisions we look at the image of the lower facets under the projection that kills the last coordinate, in particular $\pi_{d+1}(\tilde{P}_i)$. These images give us cells of a mixed subdivision, which we refer to as a *coherent mixed subdivision*.

Mixed subdivisions also form a poset as in (5). We call the minimal elements *fine mixed subdivisions*.

Example 19. Consider the following two polytopes

$$P_1 = \text{conv} \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha = (0, 0) \\ \beta = (1, 1) \end{Bmatrix} \quad P_2 = \text{conv} \begin{Bmatrix} a = (0, 0) & b = (1, 0) \\ c = (0, 1) & d = (1, 1) \end{Bmatrix}.$$

We set $P = P_1 + P_2$ equal to their Minkowski sum. In Figure 11 we see P_1, P_2 , and P along with the Minkowski cells of P . Note that the centre node has two different labels.

Figure 11

Definition 20. As in Definition 18, we fix an ordered set of polytopes $P_1, \dots, P_n \subset \mathbb{R}^d$. Let $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ be the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^n , but instead we see it as the affine basis of the hyperplane $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid x_1 + \dots + x_n = 1\} \cong \mathbb{R}^{(n-1)}$. Now set $\mu_i : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^{(n-1)}$ to be the inclusions $\mu_i(x) = (x, e_i)$. We define the *Cayley embedding* of P_1, \dots, P_n as

$$C(P_1, \dots, P_n) = \text{conv} \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n \mu_i(P_i) \right).$$

Note immediately that if $P_1 = \dots = P_n = P$ then the Cayley embedding is just the product of P with the $n - 1$ simplex. This is just since the e_i 's are the vertices of the simplex. In symbols $C(P_1, \dots, P_n) = P \times \Delta_{n-1}$.

For $P_1 + \dots + P_n = P$ as above, the Cayley Trick is an isomorphism of posets between the poset of subdivisions of the Cayley embedding $C(P_1, \dots, P_n)$ and that of the mixed subdivision

of P . This comes from intersecting a subdivided Cayley embedding with the affine plane $\mathbb{R}^d \times \{e_1 + \dots + e_n\}$. Here there is an issue of scaling, where what we technically get when doing this intersection is a scaled version of the Minkowski sum P . We ignore this, as we only care about the combinatorial aspect of the subdivision. The following formulation comes from Theorem 1.4 in [DLRS10].

Theorem 21. (*Cayley Trick*)

1. For any polyhedral subdivision of $C(P_1, \dots, P_n)$, intersecting its cells with $\mathbb{R}^d \times \{\sum e_i\}$ we get a mixed subdivision of $\sum P_i$.
2. This correspondence is a poset isomorphism between subdivisions of $C(P_1, \dots, P_n)$ and mixed subdivisions of $\sum P_i$, and bijects regular subdivisions of $C(P_1, \dots, P_n)$ to coherent mixed subdivisions of $\sum P_i$.

Remark 22. Considering the case $P_1 = \dots = P_n = \Delta_{d-1}$, the Cayley trick gives a connection between the mixed subdivisions of the Minkowski sum $\sum_i P_i = n \cdot \Delta_{d-1}$ and the subdivisions of the Cayley embedding $C(P_1, \dots, P_n) = \Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$.

Example 23. We apply the Cayley trick to two 1-simplices, $P_1 = P_2 = \Delta_1$, to get a fine coherent mixed subdivision of the dilated 1-simplex, $2 \cdot \Delta_1 = \Delta_1 + \Delta_1$.

With the notation of the previous remark in mind, we have $C(P_1, P_2) = \Delta_1 \times \Delta_1$. Now to get a mixed subdivision of $2 \cdot \Delta_1$, we first consider a subdivision of $\Delta_1 \times \Delta_1$. There are only two options, both of which are regular.

On the left of Figure 12 we see the Cayley embedding $C(P_1, P_2)$ which is the product of simplices $\Delta_1 \times \Delta_1$ living in the hyperplane $\{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 1\}$. It is subdivided by a regular subdivision, which happens to be a triangulation. We can assign the top right node height one and the other nodes height zero to see that this subdivision is indeed regular.

On the right we have the dilated one simplex $2 \cdot \Delta_1$. We intersect the subdivided $\Delta_1 \times \Delta_1$ with the hyperplane $\mathbb{R}^1 \times \{e_1 + e_2\}$, denoted with the orange dashed line on the left. This gives a fine coherent mixed subdivision of $2 \cdot \Delta_1$. It is fine since it comes from a triangulation, and it is coherent since it comes from a regular subdivision. As noted above the intersection of the Cayley embedding with the hyperplane is a scaled version (by a factor of $\frac{1}{2}$) of the Minkowski sum.

Figure 12

1.5 Tropical Hyperplane Arrangements

In this subsection, we briefly discuss tropical hyperplane arrangements, how they arise and what it means for them to be generic. Fix a matrix $V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$. We think of the rows of V as points in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and we write v_i for the i^{th} row. We set each v_i to be the apex of a hyperplane f_i as defined in (3). We would like to formalize the idea of taking the union of these hyperplanes.

The following Lemma is an easy consequence of the Fundamental Theorem mentioned in Remark 6. See [Jos21] Lemma 4.6 for details.

Lemma 24. *The tropical hypersurface of the product of two tropical polynomials is the union of the tropical hypersurfaces,*

$$\mathcal{T}(f \odot g) = \mathcal{T}(f) \cup \mathcal{T}(g).$$

Consider the product of the linear homogeneous polynomials f_i :

$$F_V = \bigodot_{i \in [n]} f_i = \bigodot_{i \in [n]} (-v_{i1} \odot x_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus -v_{id} \odot x_d). \quad (6)$$

The previous lemma allows us to define the *tropical hyperplane arrangement induced by V* as

$$\mathcal{A}_V = \mathcal{T}(F_V) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \mathcal{T}(f_i).$$

Remark 25. Since each f_i is a homogeneous polynomial of degree one, we have that $\text{supp}(f_i) = \{e_1, \dots, e_d\}$. Hence, the f_i 's Newton polytopes is a $d - 1$ simplex, in symbols $\mathcal{N}(f_i) = \Delta_{d-1}$. Similarly, F_V will be a homogeneous polynomial now of degree n , so we have $\mathcal{N}(F_V) = n \cdot \Delta_{d-1}$. This notation can be thought of in two ways: as n -times the Minkowski sum $\Delta_{d-1} + \cdots + \Delta_{d-1}$, or as the dilation of Δ_{d-1} by a factor of n . Both yield the same polytope. See the previous subsection for more about the Minkowski sum.

The previous remark should remind the reader of the Cayley trick and the discussion surrounding it in the previous subsection. Specifically see Remark 22. Applying this to the dual subdivisions of polynomials defined in the first subsection we get the following as a corollary to the Cayley trick (Theorem 21).

Corollary 26. *The dual subdivision $\mathcal{S}(F_V) = \mathcal{S}(f_1 \odot \cdots \odot f_n)$ of the Newton polytope $\mathcal{N}(F_V) = \mathcal{N}(f_1) + \cdots + \mathcal{N}(f_n)$, which is a coherent mixed subdivision is isomorphic to the regular subdivision of the Cayley embedding $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{F}_V) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{N}(f_1), \dots, \mathcal{N}(f_n))$ induced by height function V .*

In the linear homogeneous polynomial case this gives an equivalence of the regular subdivision of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ induced by V and the dual subdivision $\mathcal{S}(F_V)$ of $n \cdot \Delta_{d-1}$. As mentioned, we would like a tropical analog to a hyperplane arrangement being generic. In the case of classical hyperplanes we use the determinant, for our purposes we look at its tropicalization.

Definition 27. With S_n as the symmetric group of n elements. We define, for a square matrix $A \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times d}$, the *tropical determinant* as

$$\text{tdet}(A) = \bigoplus_{\sigma \in S_n} a_{1\sigma(1)} \odot \cdots \odot a_{d\sigma(d)}.$$

We say A is *tropically singular* if the minimum in $\text{tdet}(A)$ equals ∞ or is attained at least twice. Otherwise we say A is *tropically regular*.

With this definition we have made precise what we hinted at in Remark 13.

Remark 28. A connection to optimization arises here. Evaluating the tropical determinant is related to solving the linear assignment problem. The linear assignment is often formulated as finding the minimum matching (of some size, or the perfect matching) of a weighted bipartite graph. For the matrix $A \in T^{d \times d}$, we consider the bipartite graph B with two parts $[d] = \{1, \dots, d\}$ and $[d'] = \{1', \dots, d'\}$. If the entry $a_{ij} < \infty$ we say B has the edge (i, j') with weight a_{ij} . Evaluating $\text{tdet}(A)$ as in Definition 27 is like trying to find the minimum perfect matching of the bipartite graph B . We get $\text{tdet}(A) = \infty$ if there is no perfect matching of B , in which case we say A is singular. If there is more than one optimal perfect matching of B , we also say A is singular. When there is a unique optimal perfect matching of B , we say A is regular. For more details see Chapter 3 of [Jos21].

For V as above, we say V is *tropically generic* if all of its maximal minors are tropically regular. We refer to the point configuration or the tropical hyperplane arrangement that V represents as tropically generic if V is. The following statement, gives us a geometric reason as to why we refer to the point configuration/hyperplane arrangement of V as generic.

Proposition 29. ([Jos21], Theorem 4.14) *The following are equivalent:*

- (i) *The matrix V is tropically generic.*
- (ii) *There is an $\epsilon > 0$ such that for every matrix $D \in [0, \epsilon)^{m \times d}$ the coherent mixed subdivisions $\mathcal{S}(F_{V+D})$ and $\mathcal{S}(F_V)$ agree.*
- (iii) *The coherent mixed subdivision $\mathcal{S}(F_V)$ of $\text{supp}(F_V)$ is fine.*
- (iv) *The corresponding regular subdivision of $C(F_V)$ is a triangulation.*

Example 30. We look at an example of two max tropical hyperplane arrangements coming from the following two matrices/point configurations.

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \quad U = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

As in our discussion, we use the rows to define max tropical linear forms.

$$f_1 = t \boxplus x \boxplus y$$

$$f_2 = t \boxplus -3 \odot x \boxplus -1 \odot y$$

$$f_3 = t \boxplus -2 \odot x \boxplus 1 \odot y$$

$$f_4 = t \boxplus 1 \odot x \boxplus -2 \odot y$$

$$g_1 = t \boxplus x \boxplus y$$

$$g_2 = t \boxplus -3 \odot x \boxplus y$$

$$g_3 = t \boxplus -2 \odot x \boxplus 1 \odot y$$

$$g_4 = t \boxplus x \boxplus -2 \odot y$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_V &= f_1 \odot f_2 \odot f_3 \odot f_4 \\ &= t^4 \boxplus 1 \odot t^3 x \boxplus 1 \odot t^2 x^2 \boxplus -1 \odot t x^3 \\ &\quad \boxplus -4 \odot x^4 \boxplus 1 \odot t^3 y \boxplus 2 \odot t^2 xy \\ &\quad \boxplus 2 \odot t x^2 y \boxplus -1 \odot x^3 y \boxplus 1 \odot t^2 y^2 \\ &\quad \boxplus 2 \odot t x y^2 \boxplus 1 \odot x^2 y^2 \boxplus t y^3 \\ &\quad \boxplus 1 \odot x y^3 \boxplus -2 \odot y^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_U &= g_1 \odot g_2 \odot g_3 \odot g_4 \\ &= t^4 \boxplus t^3 x \boxplus t^2 x^2 \boxplus -2 \odot t x^3 \\ &\quad \boxplus -5 \odot x^4 \boxplus 1 \odot t^3 y \boxplus 1 \odot t^2 xy \\ &\quad \boxplus 1 \odot t x^2 y \boxplus -2 \odot x^3 y \boxplus 1 \odot t^2 y^2 \\ &\quad \boxplus 1 \odot t x y^2 \boxplus 1 \odot x^2 y^2 \boxplus 1 \odot t y^3 \\ &\quad \boxplus 1 \odot x y^3 \boxplus -1 \odot y^4 \end{aligned}$$

Visualizing the tropical hypersurfaces of these two polynomials gives us the following max tropical hyperplane arrangements, in Figure 13.

(a) $\mathcal{A}_V^{\max} = \mathcal{T}(F_V)$ which is in tropically generic position.

(b) $\mathcal{A}_U^{\max} = \mathcal{T}(G_U)$ which is not in tropically generic position.

Figure 13

These arrangements are dual to the coherent mixed subdivisions of the dilated 2-simplex $4 \cdot \Delta_2$, see Figure 14.

We can see that the matrix V above is regular, while the matrix U is singular.

The sign of the ordinary determinant has important uses such as classifying orientability. The sign of the tropical determinate will also be useful to us later.

Definition 31. The *tropical sign*, written tsgn , assigns a square matrix $A \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times d}$ an element of the set $\{-1, 0, 1\}$. If A is tropically singular, as in Definition 27, we have $\text{tsgn}(A) = 0$. If A is tropically regular then $\text{tsgn}(A)$ is equal to the sign of the unique permutation that attains the minimum/maximum.

(a) This coherent mixed subdivision is fine.

(b) This coherent mixed subdivision is not fine.

Figure 14: The coherent mixed subdivisions dual to the arrangements above. The mixed subdivision is fine if and only if the corresponding hyperplane arrangement is generic.

2 Weighted Digraphs

Working in \mathbb{R}^d with coordinates x_1, \dots, x_d , we consider systems of inequalities where all the inequalities are of the type

$$x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij}, \quad w_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Systems of this type have a clear connection with the incidence matrices of digraphs. Note that these inequalities are of the same form as the hyperplanes described in Proposition 7 (v). Starting with a weighted digraph Γ on the node set $[d] = \{1, \dots, d\}$, each arc of the digraph can be used to describe an inequality. The arc (i, j) between nodes i and j in $[d]$ with weight w_{ij} , describes the inequality above. We refer to polyhedra defined this way as *weighted digraph polyhedra*. In this section we construct weighted digraph polyhedra and show their main properties. We later show that polytopes, introduced in subsection 1.3, are bounded weighted digraph polyhedra. We also introduce envelopes, which allow us to talk about tropical convexity using graph theoretic language. This section provides the background for subsection 3.2. The main reference for this section is [JL16].

2.1 Weighted Digraph Polyhedra

We begin with a $d \times d$ matrix W with entries in \mathbb{T} . We define $\Gamma(W)$ as a weighted digraph with node set $[d]$. $\Gamma(W)$ has arc (i, j) with weight w_{ij} if the entry $w_{ij} < \infty$. Note that we can construct W if we are only given a weighted digraph Γ . W and Γ contain the same information, so we may use them interchangeably. We define a *weighted digraph polyhedron* $Q(W)$ in \mathbb{R}^d as the intersection of the halfspaces

$$x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij} \quad (i, j) \in \Gamma(W).$$

Notice immediately, by the form of the inequalities, that $Q(W)$ will have the subspace $\mathbb{R}(1, \dots, 1) = \mathbb{R}\mathbf{1}$ in its lineality space. Thus, it is natural to view it in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. Next, we introduce a running example, which we have already seen before in the context of tropical convexity.

Example 32. Given the following matrix W , we consider the inequality system it defines. Figure 15(a) we show its weighted digraph $\Gamma(W)$. Then in Figure 15(b) and (c) we visualize the polyhedron $Q(W)$ first in \mathbb{R}^3 , where it is defined, then in $\mathbb{TA}^2 \cong \mathbb{R}^2$, where it "naturally lives".

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 4 & 5 \\ -1 & 0 & 2 \\ -2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$Q(W) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \\ x_2 - x_1 \leq 4 \\ x_3 - x_1 \leq 5 \\ x_1 - x_2 \leq -1 \\ x_3 - x_2 \leq 2 \\ x_1 - x_3 \leq -2 \\ x_2 - x_3 \leq 0 \end{array} \right\} \subset \mathbb{R}^3, \quad Q(W)/\mathbb{R}\mathbf{1} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{TA}^2, \\ x \leq 4 \\ y \leq 5 \\ -x \leq -1 \\ y - x \leq 2 \\ -y \leq -2 \\ x - y \leq 0 \end{array} \right\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^2 \cong \mathbb{R}^2.$$

(a) $\Gamma(W)$.

(b) $Q(W) \subset \mathbb{R}^3$.

(c) $Q(W) \subset \mathbb{TA}^2 \cong \mathbb{R}^2$.

Figure 15

Remark 33. It is clear from the definitions above that if the weighted digraph $\Gamma(W)$ has a negative cycle, then the polyhedron $Q(W)$ will be empty. So in what follows we assume that $\Gamma(W)$ has no negative cycles.

Another fact immediate from the definition is that the intersection of two weighted digraph polyhedra is again a weighted digraph polyhedron. Given $Q(W)$ and $Q(W')$ we have that

$$Q(W) \cap Q(W') = Q(W \oplus W').$$

where \oplus here is the entry wise minimum. The arc set of $\Gamma(W \oplus W')$ is the union of the arcs sets of $\Gamma(W)$ and $\Gamma(W')$.

Remark 34. For a matrix $W \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times d}$ we define its *Kleene star*, W^* as the shortest path matrix, w_{ij}^* is the length of the shortest path with target node i and source node j . See Example 72 for an example of when $\Gamma(W^*)$ looks different from $\Gamma(W)$. We have the following formula for computing W^* , which we write using tropical matrix arithmetic

$$W^* = I \oplus W \oplus \dots \oplus W^{\odot d}. \quad (7)$$

Note that the identity matrix in the tropical world has zeros off the diagonal and ∞ 's on the diagonal. Evaluating the above expression is computationally similar to running the Bellman-Ford algorithm on $\Gamma(W)$.

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \dots & \infty \\ \infty & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \infty \\ \infty & \dots & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Note that W^* will always have zeros on its diagonal, because the 0 length path will always be the shortest path from a node to itself.

Lemma 35. (Lemmas 2 and 3, [JL16]) For a matrix $W \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times d}$ and W^* as its Kleene star we have:

- (i) Each of the inequalities that define $Q(W^*)$ are tight.
- (ii) $Q(W) = Q(W^*)$.

Proof

- (i) Fix $i \in [d]$, we claim that the row vector $w_i^* = (w_{i1}, \dots, w_{id})$ satisfies the equality $x_j - x_k = w_{kj}^*$ for all j and k in $[d]$. We see that this is true by the definition of W^* as the shortest path matrix of the digraph Γ . We have

$$w_{ij}^* \leq w_{ik}^* + w_{kj}^* \iff w_{ij}^* - w_{ik}^* \leq w_{kj}^*.$$

Recalling that $w_{ii}^* = 0$ for all $i \in [d]$ completes the argument. Note that this implies the row vectors of W^* describe a point in $Q(W^*)$ that is tight in d inequalities.

- (ii) $Q(W^*) \subset Q(W)$ is immediate since the bounds are tighter and there are more inequalities. To see the other inclusion, suppose $P = (1, \dots, r)$ is a path in $\Gamma(W)$. We can label P like this without loss of generality. The path P corresponds to the inequalities $x_{i+1} - x_i \leq w_{i+1}$ for $i \in [r]$. Adding up all those inequalities we get

$$x_r - x_1 \leq \sum_{i=2}^r w_{i-1, i}.$$

now if P was the shortest path with target node r and source node 1, then this inequality is valid for $Q(W^*)$, hence we have $Q(W) \subset Q(W^*)$.

□

Remark 36. In [JL16] the Weyl–Minkowski decomposition of a general $Q(W)$ is discussed. The recession cone of $Q(W)$ is proven to be $Q(\Gamma, 0)$, the weighted digraph polyhedron attained from setting all the weights of the digraph to be zero.

A digraph G is *strongly connected*, if for any two nodes i and j in G there exists a path in G from i to j and a path from j to i . Similarly, G is *weakly connected* if for any two nodes i and

j in G there exists in G a path from i to j or a path from j to i . This allows us to refer to the strongly connected or weakly connected components of a general digraph.

In [JL16] it is also shown that the lineality space of a weighted digraph polyhedron has dimension equal to the number of weakly connected components of the digraph Γ . See section 2.3 and 2.4 of [JL16] for details. For our purposes we will only deal with bounded weighted digraph polyhedra. A weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(W)$ is bounded if and only if $\Gamma(W)$ is strongly connected (Corollary 16, [JL16]).

In general, we get the faces of a polyhedron by setting some of its inequalities to equality. For weighted digraph polyhedra we describe faces of $Q(W)$ by subgraphs. Let F be a face of our weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(W)$. We construct an unweighted subgraph of $\Gamma(W)$ (on the same node set) to describe F , we denote this subgraph $\Gamma(W)_F$, or simply Γ_F . Consider the collection of inequalities that must be set to equality to describe F , denote this as $\text{eq}(F)$ where elements are 2-tuples (i, j) with $i, j \in [d]$. As in the construction above, the arc (i, j) corresponds to the inequality $x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij}$. Now for each $(i, j) \in \text{eq}(F)$ add the arc (i, j) to the subgraph Γ_F . Define the $d \times d$ matrix

$$(W \# \Gamma_F)_{ji} = \begin{cases} -w_{ij} & (i, j) \in \Gamma_F \\ w_{ji} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Note that this operation is not defined if we have $(i, j), (j, i) \in \Gamma_F$ and $w_{ij} \neq -w_{ji}$. This construction allows us to describe all the faces of a weighed digraph polyhedron by subgraphs of $\Gamma(W)$.

Lemma 37. ([JL16], Lemma 7) *Faces of weighted digraph polyhedra are weighted digraph polyhedra.*

$$\begin{aligned} F &= Q(W) \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d \mid x_j - x_i = w_{ij}, \text{ for all } (i, j) \in \Gamma_F\} \\ &= Q(W) \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d \mid x_i - x_j \leq -w_{ij}, \text{ for all } (i, j) \in \Gamma_F\} = Q(W \# \Gamma_F). \end{aligned}$$

See Figure 16, where we apply the lemma to our running example.

Remark 38. Being able to describe and compute projections of polyhedra is practically and theoretically useful. In the case of general polyhedra we have Fourier–Motzkin elimination which has high complexity. For weighted digraph polyhedra, projections are simpler from both a theoretical and computational point of view. For an index set $I \subset [d]$ we define the map π_I to be the projection where the coordinates with index in I are killed. For a $d \times d$ matrix W we define the operation W/I as deleting the rows and columns of W that have index in I . If $I = \{r\}$ for $r \in [d]$ we write π_r and $Q(W/r)$.

Lemma 39. ([JL16], Lemma 22) *The image of $Q(W) = Q(W^*)$ under the linear projection π_I is the weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(W^*/I)$.*

Proof. We compose projections one index at a time to get π_I . So by induction it is enough to show the result for I a singleton. Without loss of generality we assume $I = \{d\}$. First we

Figure 16: With the same weighted digraph polyhedron as in Example 32, we describe one of the faces as in Lemma 37.

show $\pi_d(Q(W^*)) \subset Q(W^*/d)$. For a point x in the image, we have that it respected all the inequalities describing $Q(W^*)$ and that is not changed by projection. For the reverse inclusion we consider $x = (x_1, \dots, x_{d-1}) \in Q(W^*/d)$. We show there exists a real number y such that $\bar{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_{d-1}, y) \in Q(W^*)$. Such a y must obey

$$x_j - w_{dj}^* \leq y \quad \text{and} \quad y \leq x_i + w_{id}^* \quad \text{for all } i, j \in [d],$$

for \bar{x} to be in $Q(W^*)$. With $p, q \in [d-1]$, we set

$$x_p - w_{dp}^* = \max_{j \in [d-1]} (x_j - w_{dj}^*) \quad \text{and} \quad x_q + w_{qd}^* = \min_{i \in [d-1]} (x_i + w_{id}^*).$$

So we just need to show

$$x_q - w_{dq}^* \leq x_p + w_{pd}^*.$$

Since $x \in Q(W^*/d)$ we have

$$x_q - x_p \leq w_{pq}^* \leq w_{dp}^* + w_{qd}^*$$

where the second inequality is by the shortest path property. \square

Example 40. With W as in Example 32, we observe the effect of the map π_3 where we kill coordinate x_3 or what we called y when in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^2$.

$$W/\{3\} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 4 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 17

2.2 Envelopes

We now consider a not necessarily square matrix $V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$, where we think of the row vectors as points in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. We also refer to V as the set of n points $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. Thus, the columns of V mark dimension while the rows mark the points. We define the envelope of V as the polyhedron

$$\mathcal{E}(V) = \{(y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^n \mid y_j - z_i \leq v_{ij} \text{ for all } j \in [d] \text{ and } i \in [n]\}. \quad (9)$$

Like with the weighted digraph polyhedra construction above, we associate a digraph to this polyhedron. This time we define a bipartite graph with the two parts as the sets $[n]$ and $[d]$, representing the rows and columns of V respectively. This definition also allows us to write $\mathcal{E}(V)$ in more graphical language.

$$\begin{aligned} B(V) &= \{(i, j) \in [n] \times [d] \mid v_{ij} \neq \infty\} \\ \mathcal{E}(V) &= \{(y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^n \mid y_j - z_i \leq v_{ij} \text{ for all } (i, j) \in B(V)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 41. Note that $\mathcal{E}(V)$ is a weighted digraph polyhedron. We define the $(n+d) \times (n+d)$ matrix

$$V_W = \begin{pmatrix} \infty_{n \times n} & V \\ \infty_{d \times n} & \infty_{d \times d} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Thus $\Gamma(V_W)$ is $B(V)$ up to relabeling. For a subgraph $G \subset B(V)$ with an arc (i, j) , $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [d]$ it will be useful to see G as a subgraph of $\Gamma(V_W)$. We refer this subgraph again as $G \subset \Gamma(V_W)$. Note that the arc $(i, j) \in G$ is now $(i, j+n)$ when seen in $\Gamma(V_W)$. To avoid cumbersome notation we say G has arcs going from $[n]$ to $[d'] = \{1', \dots, d'\}$, where $j' = j+n$ as a node of $\Gamma(V_W)$.

Remark 42. For V , seen as a set of n points $\{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ it is natural to write $v_i = (0, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{id})$ for each $i \in [n]$. That way in the $d = 3, 4$ cases we can easily visualize the points in \mathbb{R}^2 and \mathbb{R}^3 . It will also sometimes be useful to mimic the format of W^* , having zeros along the diagonal. We refer to this as shifting V , either so that the top row is all zeros, or so that the diagonal is zeros. This is always possible since the rows of the V represent points in the tropical torus $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)} = \mathbb{R}^d / \mathbb{R}\mathbf{1}$.

Example 43. For the following 3×3 matrix V we see an example of the shifting mentioned in Remark 42 and of the matrix V_W in Remark 41. We see the associated bipartite graphs in

Figure 18.

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} -5 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 4 \\ 3 & 5 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{shifted}} V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 4 & 5 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 2 & 2 \end{pmatrix} \quad V_W = \begin{pmatrix} & 0 & 4 & 5 \\ \infty_{3 \times 3} & 0 & 1 & 3 \\ & 0 & 2 & 2 \\ \infty_{3 \times 3} & \infty_{3 \times 3} & & \end{pmatrix}$$

(a) $B(V)$ squares are the rows of V (after the shift) while circles are the columns.

(b) $\Gamma(V_W)$, built from the $(n+d) \times (n+d)$ matrix described in (41).

Figure 18: Bipartite graphs of Example 43. Some arc weights are omitted to maintain readability.

In light of Remark 41, Lemma 37 tells us that we can describe the faces of the envelope using subgraphs of $B(V)$. We describe the projection of faces of the envelope. For a subgraph $B_F \subset B(V)$, define the $d \times n$ matrix

$$(V[B_F])_{ji} = \begin{cases} -v_{ij} & (i, j) \in B_F \\ \infty & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Combining this with Lemma 39 we get the following result. We rework the proof found in the literature as it will be relevant to us in section 4.1. Note that $V[B_F] \odot V$ is a $d \times d$ matrix.

Lemma 44. *Let F be a face of $\mathcal{E}(V)$ and $B_F \subset B(V)$ the subgraph that describes it. Then the image of the face F under the projection $\pi_{[n]} : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is the weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V[B_F] \odot V)$.*

Proof. We first reformulate the result in the notation of Lemma 39. As mentioned in Remark 41, $\mathcal{E}(V)$ can be seen as the weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V_W)$. In Remark 41, we noted the change a subgraph of $B(V)$ undergoes when the envelope is seen as a weighted digraph polyhedron. The projection looks like

$$\pi_{[n]}(Q(V_W \# B_F)) = Q((V_W \# B_F)^* / [n]).$$

We need to show that $(V_W \# B_F)^* / [n]$ and $V[B_F] \odot V$ give the same polyhedron. Recalling the definition of $V[B_F]$ in (10) and the power series like formula for the Kleene star of a square matrix given in (7) we compute the first two powers

$$V_W \# B_F = \begin{pmatrix} \infty_{n \times n} & V \\ V[B_F] & \infty_{d \times d} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad (V_W \# B_F)^2 = \begin{pmatrix} V \odot V[B_F] & \infty_{n \times d} \\ \infty_{d \times n} & V[B_F] \odot V \end{pmatrix}.$$

If we stop taking powers and quotient out by $[n]$ at the degree two term we would end up with the square matrix in the claim,

$$(V_W \# B_F)^2 / [n] = V[B_F] \odot V$$

We claim that the two matrices

$$(V_W \# B_F)^2 / [n] \quad \text{and} \quad (V_W \# B_F)^* / [n]. \quad (11)$$

yield the same polyhedron. With that we will have shown the result. We set

$$A = (V_W \# B_F)^2 / [n] = V[B_F] \odot V,$$

and show that

$$A^* = (V_W \# B_F)^* / [n].$$

This is enough since from Lemma 35 (ii) we have $Q(A) = Q(A^*)$. To simplify notation, set $B = (V_W \# B_F)$. Recall the notation introduced in Remark 41 where $p', q' \in [d'] = \{n+1, \dots, n+d\}$. Let b_{ij} be an entry in $B = (V_W \# B_F)$ and let $a_{p'q'}$ be an entry in $A = V[B_F] \odot V$, the lower right hand block of B^2 . We have

$$a_{p'q'} = \bigoplus_{i \in [n+d]} (b_{p'i} \odot b_{iq'}).$$

Graphically, this means that the nodes p' and q' are in the $[d']$ part, or the 'right' part of the bipartite graph $\Gamma(V_W \# B_F)$. Further, $b_{p'i}$ can be seen as the weight of an arc going from the left to the right part and $b_{iq'}$ can be seen as going back. The construction of $B(V)$ only had arcs going from left to right ($[n]$ to $[d]$) so the arcs going 'back' will come from the augmentation made by B_F . See Figure 19. From the construction of $V[B_F]$ in 10 we have that $b_{p'i} = -b_{ip'}$. With that in mind and the fact that $\Gamma(V_W)$ is bipartite meaning that we only need to consider the minimum over $i \in [n]$. We can write, this time in classical arithmetic,

$$a_{p'q'} = \min_{i \in [n]} (b_{p'i} + b_{iq'}) = \min_{i \in [n], b_{ip'} \neq \infty, b_{iq'} \neq \infty} (-b_{ip'} + b_{iq'}).$$

Figure 19 shows what this path looks like. This is exactly the shortest 2-arc-path from p' to q' . Thus the entries $a_{p'q'}$ of the matrix A encode the paths between the nodes in $[d']$ that come from the shortest 2-arc-paths. Since $\Gamma(V_W)$ is bipartite the shortest paths within either of the parts will be concatenations of the shortest 2 arc paths, which is what $A = V[B_F] \odot V$ encodes. Thus taking the Kleene star before projecting will not add any information not already found in A . In other words $A^* = (V_W \# B_F)^* / [n]$, and hence the two matrices in (11) give the same weighted digraph polyhedron. \square

Figure 19: Here the blue arcs come from the augmentation made by B_F .

Note the similarity to the construction $W\#\Gamma_F$ in the previous subsection. The connection between Γ_F and $B_F \subset B(V)$ is the subject of subsection 4.1. Since the envelope is in a high dimensional space it is difficult to consider examples that are not trivial. However even the following small example will give us an insight that will become more apparent later.

Example 45. The following matrix V describes a one-point "point configuration" in \mathbb{TA}^1 , written as a matrix. We have that $\mathcal{E}(V)$ is given by the inequality system on the right. We replace y_1, y_2, z_1 by x, y, z , to better visualize the polyhedron in \mathbb{R}^3 .

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{ll} y_1 - z_1 \leq 0 & x - z \leq 0 \\ y_2 - z_1 \leq 1 & y - z \leq 1 \end{array}$$

Figure 20 shows the polyhedron in \mathbb{R}^3 , which is something like a tent.

Figure 20: The green faces are the 'upper' facets of the polyhedron described in Example45.

We have two 2 dimensional faces of $\mathcal{E}(V)$, they are described by the subgraphs B_{F_1} and B_{F_2} of $B(V)$, as seen in Figure 21.

To see what the projection of the two faces will look like, we see how the subgraphs B_{F_1} and B_{F_2} augment the bipartite graph. To see this more easily we look at the Γ form of the bipartite graph. Take note of the 2-arc-path between the nodes in the bottom part of the graph seen in Figure 22.

Figure 21

Figure 22: Augmented $B(V)$ that give the face of an envelope

By Lemma 44 we can compute the matrices of the weighted digraph polyhedra that describe the faces of $\mathcal{E}(V)$.

$$V[B_{F_1}] \odot V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \infty \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad V[B_{F_2}] \odot V = \begin{pmatrix} \infty \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \infty & \infty \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

These two matrices give the following weighted digraphs and inequalities. We use variables x, y instead of x_1, x_2 . Note that the following weighted digraphs come from the 2-arc-paths in the last diagram. The projection just kills the top node. Figure 23 shows the digraphs after projection.

Figure 23

We finally come to Figure 24. On the left we have a polyhedral decomposition of \mathbb{R}^2 where the two cells are $Q(V[B_{F_1}] \odot V)$ and $Q(V[B_{F_2}] \odot V)$, as labelled. On the right we see the result after quotienting out $\mathbb{R}\mathbf{1}$ to end up in $\mathbb{R}^1 \cong \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^1$.

(a) $Q(V[B_{F_1}] \odot V)$ and $Q(V[B_{F_2}] \odot V)$ seen in \mathbb{R}^2

(b) The two polyhedra seen in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^1$. They are labelled in the figure to the left.

Figure 24

3 Point Configurations

To study polytropes, we study the point configurations they arise from. Fix a point configuration in the tropical torus, $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, where $v_i = (v_{i1}, \dots, v_{id})$. In this section we show that V induces a polyhedral subdivision of $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ which we call the *covector decomposition*, denoted C_V . Polytropes arise as bounded cells of this subdivision. $\text{tconv}(V)$ is the union of the bounded cells of C_V . The covector subdivision can be defined in two ways which are useful to use interchangeably. We first discuss C_V as in [DS04] where the combinatorial types of point configurations were studied. Cells of C_V were described as *type cells*. The authors of [JL16] translated the combinatorial types into the language of graph theory, we use the material of section 2 for this. For the second construction of the covector decomposition we follow [DJS12]. Here the subdivision C_V was defined with a tropical hyperplane arrangement, where the points in V are the apexes of the hyperplanes as in section 1.5 above. The hyperplane arrangement is constructed as a vanishing locus of the product of linear homogeneous polynomials. We explain the two constructions and their connection. The Duality Theorem 2, and the Cayley trick (Theorem 21) play important roles.

In Figure 25 we show a road map of this section.

Figure 25: Flow chart showing the connections to be made in this section.

3.1 Polyhedral Decomposition from Types

Fix $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, where $v_i = (v_{i1}, \dots, v_{id})$. We begin by stating what has been referred to as the *Structural Theorem of Tropical Convexity*.

Theorem 46. ([DS04], Theorem 1) *The combinatorial types of the polyhedral decomposition arising from n points in the $(d-1)$ tropical torus $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ are dual to the regular subdivisions of the product of simplices $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$.*

This subsection makes sense of the above statement and outlines its proof as in [DS04].

For $x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ we define the *type of x* with respect to V (or just the type of x when V is fixed) as the following d -tuple,

$$\text{type}_V(x) = (S_1, \dots, S_d), \quad S_j = \{i \in [n] \mid v_{ij} - x_j = \min(v_i - x_1, \dots, v_{id} - x_d)\} \subset [n]. \quad (12)$$

In words, to get the type of a point $x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ we look at the difference $x - v_i$, and then look at the coordinates where that difference is minimal. Supposing it is minimal in the j^{th} coordinate, we put i in S_j . We do this for each $v_i \in V$. Since the coordinate that attains the minimum does not have to be unique, i could be in more than one of the S_j 's. Note that every i must be in some S_j . If a d -tuple arises from $\text{type}_V(x)$ for some $x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, we say it is a *type*.

An equivalent way to define types is through

$$\lambda_i = \min\{\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \mid \lambda \odot v_i \oplus x = x\} \quad i \in [n]. \quad (13)$$

Here the set S_j contains all the indices $i \in [n]$ where $\lambda_i \odot v_i$ and x have the same j^{th} coordinate. We define the *collection of types with respect to $V \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$* as

$$\mathcal{Z}_V = \{\text{type}_V(x) \mid x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}\}. \quad (14)$$

Since all points in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ have a type, we can use types to identify regions of $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. For a d tuple $S = (S_1, \dots, S_d)$, not necessarily a type, we define

$$X_S = \{x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)} \mid S \subseteq \text{type}_V(x)\}, \quad (15)$$

" \subseteq " here means that S_i is a subset of the i^{th} entry of $\text{type}_V(x)$. Note that S is not necessarily a type. X_S is the set of all points whose type with respect to V contains S . Note that with this notion of inclusion among types we can think of $(\mathcal{Z}_V, \subseteq)^{op}$ as a partially ordered set.

Example 47. Let $V \subset \mathbb{TA}^2$ be,

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 6 \\ -2 & -1 & 1 \\ -5 & -3 & -3 \end{pmatrix},$$

where v_i is given by the i^{th} row. For $x = (-1, 2, 4) \in \mathbb{TA}^2$, we have that $\text{type}_V(x) = (\{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2, 3\})$, and for $y = (1, 4, 3)$ we have $\text{type}_V(y) = (\{1\}, \{23\}, \emptyset)$.

Much of what follows rests on the following lemma, so we include its proof.

Lemma 48. ([DS04], Lemma 10) *The set X_S is a closed polyhedron (in the ordinary convexity sense), more precisely*

$$X_S = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)} \mid x_k - x_j \leq v_{ik} - v_{ij} \text{ for all } j, k \in [n] \text{ such that } i \in S_j \right\}. \quad (16)$$

Proof. Take $x \in X_S \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. By definition of X_S we have that $S \subset \text{type}_V(x) = T$. Thus for every $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [d]$, if $i \in S_j$ we have $i \in T_j$. Then by the definition of type,

$$v_{ij} - x_j = \min\{v_{ik} - x_k \mid k \in [d]\}, \quad \text{in particular } v_{ij} - x_j \leq v_{ik} - x_k \text{ for all } k \in [d].$$

Rearranged, we have the inequality on the right hand side of (16), $x_k - x_j \leq v_{ik} - v_{ij}$, for each $i \in S_j$.

Now, take x to be in the set on the right hand side of (16). With $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [d]$ we rearrange the defining inequalities to get that, if $i \in S_j$ then $v_{ij} - x_j \leq v_{ik} - x_k$ for all $k \in [d]$. Hence $v_{ij} - x_j = \min\{v_{ik} - x_k \mid k \in [d]\}$, which is to say $i \in T_j$. So $S_j \subset T_j = \text{type}_V(x)$, and $x \in X_S$. \square

We can immediately state a sort of converse to the previous lemma. This connects a class of ordinary polyhedra to the type cells we have just constructed. The reader should be reminded of the weighted digraph polyhedra of section 2. The following proposition has a counterpart in the next subsection, when we relate type cells to weighted digraph polyhedra.

Proposition 49. ([DS04], Proposition 18) *Let P be a polyhedron in \mathbb{R}^d that is defined by inequalities of the form $x_j - x_i \leq c_{ji}$. In particular P is a polytope in the tropical torus $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. Then for some point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$, P arises as a type cell of V .*

The following proposition summarizes all of the nice properties of type cells. For details see section 3 of [DS04].

Proposition 50. ([DS04]) *Fix an n -point set $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ in the $(d-1)$ -tropical torus and a point $x \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. Fix also the d -tuples $S = (S_1, \dots, S_d)$ and $T = (T_1, \dots, T_d)$, where S_j and T_j are subsets of $[n]$ for all $j \in [d]$. We refer to the type cells of V as defined in (15). We have,*

- (i) *The intersection of polyhedra $X_S \cap X_T = X_{S \cup T}$.*
- (ii) *X_S is bounded if and only if $S_j \neq \emptyset$ for each $j \in [d]$.*
- (iii) *If $\bigcup_i S_i = [n]$, then we have for $T \supset S$, X_T is a face of X_S . Moreover, all faces of X_S arise this way.*
- (iv) *If $\bigcup_i S_i = [n]$, then there exists a type $T \in \mathcal{Z}_V$ such that $X_S = X_T$.*

These properties show that the type cells are very well behaved with respect to the types (the combinatorial data) that define them. This lets us consider the collection of them. Since every point in the tropical torus has a type, we see that this collection forms a polyhedral complex that decomposes $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. Note that (iii) is similar to Lemma 37.

Theorem 51. Fix a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and set \mathcal{Z}_V as the collection of types with respect to V . We have that the collection of polyhedra X_S , where $S \in \mathcal{Z}_V$, defines a polyhedral complex C_V that decomposes the tropical torus $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. Furthermore the tropical polytope $P = \text{tconv}(V)$ is equal to the union of all bounded cells in C_V .

Proof. The roman numbers in brackets refer to the statements of the previous proposition. Since every point in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ has a type, we know that $\cup_{S \in \mathcal{Z}_V} X_S = \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. By (iii), the faces of each X_S are given by X_A where $A \supset S$. Statement (iv) gives a type $B \in \mathcal{Z}_V$ such that $X_A = X_B$. Hence the faces of each X_S are in C_V .

To show that C_V is a polyhedral complex we must show that for $S, T \in \mathcal{Z}_V$, $X_S \cap X_T$ is a face of both X_S and X_T . By (i) we have that $X_S \cap X_T = X_{S \cup T}$ and (iii) gives that $X_{S \cup T}$ is a face of both X_S and X_T , since $S, T \subset S \cup T$.

To see the second part of the statement consider $x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ with $\text{type}_V(x) = S = (S_1, \dots, S_d)$. We claim that $x \in P$ if and only if there is no $j \in [d]$ such that $S_j = \emptyset$. Once we prove this claim, statement (ii) gives the result since the bounded cells are precisely the ones with no empty entries.

Let $\lambda_i = \min\{\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \mid \lambda \odot v_i \oplus x = x\}$ as in (13). We define

$$\phi_V(x) = \lambda_1 \odot v^1 \oplus \dots \oplus \lambda_n \odot v^n.$$

We either have $\phi_V(x) = x$ or $\phi_V(x) \neq x$. The case $\phi_V(x) = x$ implies that $x \in P$, since $\phi_V(x)$ is a tropical convex combination of the points in V .

For the case $\phi_V(x) \neq x$ we set $\phi_V(x) = y$ and use the definition of the λ_i 's. We have $y_j \neq x_j$ for some $j \in [d]$, we also have that $y_j = (\lambda_i \odot v_i)_j$ for some $i \in [n]$. Hence we can write

$$x_j \neq (\lambda_i \odot v_i)_j \quad \text{for all } i \in [n].$$

This implies that $i \notin S_j$. Thus we can conclude that $\phi_V(x) \neq x$ if and only if there is a $j \in [n]$ such that $S_j = \emptyset$. This proves the claim and completes the proof. \square

Example 52. Take $V = \{(0, 4, 5), (0, 1, 3), (0, 2, 2)\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^2$ as a point configuration in the 2-tropical torus. In Figure 26, we visualize the decomposition C_V it induces of the tropical torus \mathbb{TA}^2 and the Hasse diagram of the fact poset \mathcal{Z}_V .

With the above, we can now make the notion of a *combinatorial type* of a point configuration precise. Each cell of the polyhedral complex induced by a point configuration is labelled by its type. Thus two distinct point configurations $V, W \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ have the same combinatorial type if the types occurring in C_V and in C_W are identical. Note that by Proposition 50 this means that the face posets of C_V and C_W are then also identical.

To prove Theorem 46, stated at the beginning of the subsection, we start by constructing an unbounded polyhedron in a high dimensional space. Consider the $(d + n - 1)$ dimensional real vector space $E = (\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^n) / (\mathbb{1}_n, -\mathbb{1}_d)$ where $\mathbb{1}_n$ is the all ones vector of length n and similarly with $\mathbb{1}_d$. Let the coordinates of E be $(y, z) = (y_1, \dots, y_d, z_1, \dots, z_n)$. We fix our point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, with $v_i = (v_{i1}, \dots, v_{id})$. Define

$$\mathcal{P}(V) = \{(y, z) \in E \mid y_j + z_i \leq v_{ij} \text{ for all } j \in [d] \text{ and } i \in [n]\}. \quad (17)$$

Figure 26: The polyhedral subdivision induced by V along with the Hasse diagram of its face poset \mathcal{Z}_V . The faces are described by which vertices they contain. The tuples contain elements from $\{1, 2, 3\}$ these represent the tropical vertices which are in yellow. The tropical vertices have the labels 4, 5, 6 in the diagram. The code for this visualization can be found in section 5.

This should be compared to the definition of an envelope in (9).

The polyhedron $\mathcal{P}(V)$ will be the bridge between the point configurations in the tropical torus and the product of simplices $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ as in Theorem 46. We first see how it relates to point configurations.

Lemma 53. (Lemma 22, [DS04]) Fix $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and let C_V be the polyhedral complex generated by V , as above. Then there is a piecewise linear isomorphism between the subcomplex of bounded cells of C_V , and the complex of bounded faces of the polyhedron $\mathcal{P}(V)$. The image of a bounded cell $X_S \in C_V$ under this isomorphism is the bounded face $\{y_j + z_i = v_{ij} \mid i \in S_j\}$ of $\mathcal{P}(V)$. This bounded face maps isomorphically to X_S via the projection onto the y -coordinates.

Proof. Since in the definition of E we quotiented out by the potential lineality space of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ we may consider its bounded faces.

For a bounded face F of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ we construct a type S of V such that X_S is a bounded type cell of C_V . We then show that the projection onto the y -coordinates is an affine isomorphism from F to its image. We denote this projection $\pi_{[n]}$.

Since F is bounded we have that some of the inequalities in (17) will be equalities. We construct a d -tuple $S = (S_1, \dots, S_d)$. If $y_j + z_i = v_{ij}$ holds for all $(y, z) \in F$ we put i in S_j . Claim that for each $i \in [n]$ there is a $j \in [d]$ such that $i \in S_j$ and further S_j is not empty for each $j \in [d]$. Suppose not, then there is an i or a j such that the variable y_j or z_i does not appear in any of the equalities $y_j + z_i = v_{ij}$. If this is true then we can subtract arbitrary positive multiples of the corresponding basis vector to obtain elements of F . If y_j does not appear in any equality then

$$\text{for all } (y, z) \in F \quad \text{we have} \quad (y, z) - \alpha(e_j, 0) \in F, \quad \text{for any } \alpha \geq 0.$$

This contradicts that F is bounded, proving the claim. For a point $y \in \pi_{[n]}(F)$ in the image of a bounded face under the projection onto the y coordinates we can use the equalities defining F to find a unique preimage. We get uniqueness since by the claim we have that each z_i appears in some equality. Thus $\pi_{[n]}$ is an affine isomorphism onto its image.

We now want to show that $\pi_{[n]}(F)$ is equal to the type cell X_S with the S from above. We fix a point $y \in \pi_{[n]}(F)$ coming from the relative interior of F , and show $y \in X_S$. Recall from Lemma 48 that for y to be in X_S it must obey the defining inequalities, which are of the form $y_j - y_k \leq v_{ij} - v_{ik}$. From the definition of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ and our construction of S , we have that

$$\text{for all } i \in [n] \quad y_j \leq v_{ij} - z_i \quad \text{and for all } i \in S_j \quad y_j = v_{ij} - z_i. \quad (18)$$

Subtracting $y_k \leq v_{ik} - z_i$ from the equality in (18) shows that y satisfies X_S 's defining inequalities and is thus in X_S . Since y came from the relative interior of F , adding any more equalities will take it to a face of F . In the context of our construction of S , that means S is the maximal d -tuple that gives the type cell X_S . By Proposition 50 (iv) this means $\text{type}_V(y) = S$.

Now fix $y \in X_S$, we need to find z such that $(y, z) \in F$. We have that $\text{type}_V(y) = S$, so we use the definition of type in (12) to find z . Define

$$z_i = \min\{v_{i1} - y_1, \dots, v_{id} - y_d\}.$$

Now $y_j + z_i \leq v_{ij}$ for each i and j so $(y, z) \in \mathcal{P}(V)$. For $i \in S_j$ we have that $y_j + z_i = v_{ij}$ so $(y, z) \in F$.

Finally, we argue that the two complexes are isomorphic, in particular, they have the same face poset. Suppose we have F, G faces of $\mathcal{P}(V)$. With the above we have that $\pi_{[n]}(F) = X_S$ and $\pi_{[n]}(G) = X_T$ such that S and T are types with respect to V . From Proposition 50 (iii) that X_S is a face of X_T if and only if $T \subset S$. Above we saw that the type of the image of a bounded face of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ describes its equalities. So $T \subset S$ tells us that the equalities that G satisfies (described by T) are a subset of the equalities that F satisfies. This means that F is a face of G . Hence X_S is a face of X_T if and only if F is a face of G , and with that the complexes are isomorphic. \square

The poset of types $(\mathcal{Z}, \subseteq)^{op}$ defined above is isomorphic to the face poset of the polyhedral decomposition \mathcal{C}_V .

Now we see how $\mathcal{P}(V)$ relates to the product of simplices $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$. We recall a basic definition from polyhedral geometry.

Definition 54. For a polytope $P \subset \mathbb{R}^m$ with vertices $\{p_1, \dots, p_l\}$, we define using the euclidean inner product the *polar of P* as

$$P^\vee = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid \langle p_k, x \rangle \leq 1 \text{ for all } k \in [l]\}.$$

We set $P = \Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ in the definition above. Now note that the vertices p_k are of the form (e_j, e_i) for $j \in [d]$ and $i \in [n]$. Here e_j marks the j^{th} standard basis vector of \mathbb{R}^d and likewise with e_i in \mathbb{R}^n . Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1})^\vee &= \{(y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^n \mid \langle (e_j, e_i), (y, z) \rangle \leq 1 \text{ for all } j \in [d] \text{ and } i \in [n]\} \\ &= \{(y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^n \mid y_j + z_i \leq 1 \text{ for all } j \in [d] \text{ and } i \in [n]\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we have the result that the regular subdivision of a polytope P is polar to the facet complex of its polar P^\vee . The technical result is spelled out in [DLRS10] section 9.5.1, more specifically in Theorem 9.5.6. There the authors use the language of central and normal fans. For us this means that the boundary complex of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ is polar to the regular subdivision of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$. Intuitively this means that a subset of vertices (e_j, e_i) of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ form a cell of the regular subdivision if and only if the corresponding equalities $y_j + z_i = v_{ij}$ form a face of $\mathcal{P}(V)$. We are now ready to prove Theorem 46.

Proof. The combinatorial structure of the polyhedron $\mathcal{P}(V)$ (its face poset) is completely determined by the lists of facets containing the bounded faces. In Lemma 53 we showed that these lists are the type of the bounded type cells of the decomposition \mathcal{C}_V . On the other hand, from the discussion immediately above we have that the poset of bounded faces of $\mathcal{P}(V)$ is anti-isomorphic to the poset of interior cells of the regular subdivision of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$. All full dimensional cells of the regular subdivision are interior and hence determine the entire poset of the subdivision. \square

Recall from subsection 1.5 what it means for a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ to be in tropically generic position. Roughly, we have that the combinatorial type of V does not

change under small perturbations. This statement can be seen as a consequence of Proposition 29.

Proposition 55. *(Proposition 24 [DS04] and Lemma 5.1 [RGST05]) Let $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ be a point configuration in the tropical torus. Then the regular subdivision of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ induced by V is a triangulation if and only if the point configuration V is tropically generic.*

3.2 Decomposition from Envelopes

The Structural Theorem of Tropical Convexity 46 proven in the previous subsection is reformulated into graph theoretic language in [JL16], which is more natural for our purposes. For the definition of an envelope, see subsection 2.2. We will use subpolytopes and regular subdivisions, which were introduced in section 1.4.

We fix a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ in the tropical torus. Recall the product of simplices

$$\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1} = \text{conv} \{(e_i, e_j) \mid (i, j) \in [d] \times [n]\},$$

and note that any of its subpolytopes can be described by a subgraph of the complete bipartite graph $K_{d,n}$. The following theorem gives a regular subdivision of the subpolytope of $\Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1}$ that is described by the edges in $B(V)$.

Theorem 56. *(Theorem 21, [JL16]) The boundary complex of the envelope $\mathcal{E}(V)$ is dual to the regular subdivision of the polytope*

$$\text{conv} \{(e_i, e_j) \mid (i, j) \in B(V)\},$$

with height function V .

Remark 57. Comparing this to the results in the previous subsection we would like to extend this regular subdivision of the subpolytope to the full product of simplices. Lemma 4.3.4 of [DLRS10] tells us we can do that. We just have to replace the entries of V that are ∞ by sufficiently large real numbers. In particular they need to be larger than all the non infinite entries of V .

Following the steps of the previous subsection, we now need to show how $V \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ induces a polyhedral subdivision of the tropical torus. This was the construction of the type cells labelled X_S in (15). The method here is analogous to the one in [JL16] and for that reason we do not include all the details. However, we remark on some details important to us. The reader can recall Example 45 to help with intuition.

First, the polyhedral decomposition of one point $u \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ is discussed. With weighted digraph polyhedra and the envelope in mind, we want to consider inequalities of the form $x_i - x_j \leq w_{ij}$. We want u to give us the weights on the right hand side, since in Theorem 56 it was the points that gave the height function to the regular subdivision. This leads us to consider the max sectors of u as we defined in (4). The max sectors of u make up the full dimensional

Figure 27: The hexagon in the middle of Figure (a) is the intersection of the three max sectors. This cell is labelled by the covector graph H in (b). Recall the max sector numbering in (c).

cells of a polyhedral decomposition denoted $\Delta(u)$; see Lemma 26 in [JL16] for details. For $i \in [d]$ the i^{th} max sector of u can be written as

$$\left\{ x \in \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)} \mid \max_{k \in [d]} (x_k - u_k) = x_i - u_i \right\}. \quad (19)$$

Now considering the full point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$. The analogous polyhedra to the type cells in the previous section are the weighted digraph polyhedra

$$X_G(V) = \bigcap_{(i,j) \in G} S_i(v_j), \quad (20)$$

where G is a subgraph of $B(V)$ as discussed in Lemma 44. See an example of such a weighted digraph polyhedron in Figure 27. Due to the nice structure of weighted digraph polyhedra and Lemmas 39 and 44 we get the following result.

Proposition 58. (Proposition 30, [JL16]) *Consider a subgraph G of $B(V)$, which we can also see as the subgraph of $\Gamma(V_W)$. The orthogonal projection of the face of the envelope $\mathcal{E}(V)$ induced by G equals $X_G(V)$. In symbols,*

$$\pi_{[n]}(Q(V_W \# G)) = Q(V[G] \odot V) = X_G(V).$$

Moreover, if no node in $[n]$ is isolated in G , we have that projection is an affine isomorphism.

The first equality is already known to us and is explained further in section 4.1, but for now should be understandable given Remark 41.

In this context, the covector decomposition is defined as the common refinement of the complexes $\Delta(v_i)$ for $i \in [n]$. The subgraphs of $B(V)$ that uniquely describe the cells of the covector decomposition are called *covector graphs*. These contain the same information as the types of the type cells above.

The use of max sectors gives a hint towards a different way of constructing the covector decomposition. That is, from a hyperplane arrangement or analogously as the product of homogeneous polynomials of degree one. This is the subject of subsection 3.3.

We can now state the desired reformulation of Theorem 46.

Theorem 59. (Corollary 34, [JL16]) *The covector decomposition $C(V)$ induced by $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ is dual to the regular subdivision of the subpolytope*

$$\text{conv}\{(e_i, e_j) \mid (i, j) \in B(V)\} \subset \Delta_{d-1} \times \Delta_{n-1},$$

with height function V . Furthermore, the decomposition of $\text{tconv}(V)$ induced by $C(V)$ is dual to the poset of interior cells of the regular subdivision.

See sections 3.1 and 3.2 of [JL16] for details. There, the possibility of ∞ as an entry in V is also considered.

3.3 Decompositions from Hyperplane Arrangements and Coarse Types

Again we fix a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ in the tropical torus, and we also refer to V as an $n \times d$ matrix where the points are the rows. In the previous two subsections we defined the covector decomposition C_V of the tropical torus induced by V . There, C_V arose from placing the points of V in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and then carving out regions that had similar combinatorial properties with respect to V .

In a sense, this subsection does the opposite. Motivated by our earlier discussion of tropical hyperplanes and their arrangements, we consider the union of the subdivisions induced by each individual point of V . The individual subdivision of a point is referred to as the *fan* of a point in [DS04]. The fact that these fans arise from tropical polynomials, homogeneous linear ones in particular, gives us more tools to use. Section 1 contains all the background we need in this subsection.

When comparing the covector decomposition C_V with the tropical hyperplane arrangement \mathcal{A}_V it will be necessary to use min and max at the same time. This was seen in the previous subsection when we defined the weighted digraph polyhedra $X_G(V)$ seen in (20).

Remark 60. In the previous two subsections we defined the covector decomposition with the convection of \oplus being the min. While this is our preferred choice there is no real reason to choose it over max. Everything in the previous two sections can be defined in the same way for $\mathbb{T}_{\max} = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\}, \boxplus, \odot)$.

As in subsection 1.5, we let each point of V define a point configuration and set \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} to be its max tropical hyperplane arrangement. Now with an ordering of the points and the

numbering of the max sectors (as mentioned in Remark 4) of each tropical hyperplane we can give labels to the cells that make up the polyhedral complex created by \mathcal{A}_V . These labels are referred to as *fine types* in some sources such as [DJS12] or [Jos21]. Recall from the previous subsection the definition of the weighted digraph polyhedron $X_G(V)$ in (20). In that definition, the covector graph G described a region of $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ by specifying which max sectors of which points contained it. In fact, to define the fine types of the tropical hyperplane arrangement \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} would be to rewrite the contents of (19) and (20). The following remark restates this equivalence slightly differently.

Remark 61. ([JL16], Remark 32) The covector decomposition C_V can be deduced from the max-tropical linear forms corresponding to the rows of V . For this, we choose variables x_{i1}, \dots, x_{id} for each row v_i of the matrix V . The product of the tropical linear forms $\max(x_{i1} - v_{i1}, \dots, x_{id} - v_{id})$ yields a homogeneous tropical polynomial F_V in the $d \cdot n$ variables x_{ij} . This defines a tropical hypersurface in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(n \cdot d)}$. Here the covector graphs are the same as the exponent vectors of the monomials of F_V . This can be seen as the variable x_{ij} being in the monomial if the arc $(i, j) \in G$. Substituting x_{ij} by y_j gives rise to the tropical hypersurface in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ which defines the covector decomposition.

The previous remark is somehow saying that the covector decomposition coming from the arrangement \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} not only arises as $\mathcal{T}(F_V)$, but also has the data of the factorization of F_V into linear homogeneous forms. Recall from subsection 1.5 that the Newton polytope of F_V is the n -dilated $d-1$ simplex $n \cdot \Delta_{d-1}$. Putting this together with our discussion of the Cayley trick from subsection 1.4, we have that knowing the factorization is like remembering the Minkowski decomposition of the Newton polytope $\mathcal{N}(F_V) = n \cdot \Delta_{d-1}$. Thus through the duality theorem and the Cayley trick we have the following version of the Structural Theorem of Tropical Convexity (Theorem 46).

Theorem 62. *Fix a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$ in the tropical torus. Let \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} be the max tropical hyperplane arrangement defined by taking the union of the max tropical linear forms $\max(x_{i1} - v_{i1}, \dots, x_{id} - v_{id})$, or equivalently defined as the tropical hypersurface of the tropical product of those max tropical linear forms. Then the polyhedral decomposition of the tropical torus arising from the arrangement is dual to the regular subdivision of the product of simplices $\Delta_{n-1} \times \Delta_{d-1}$ induced by height function V .*

Example 63. We consider the same point arrangement as in our running example.

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 4 & 5 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 2 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The rows of V define the following max tropical linear homogeneous polynomials.

$$f_1 = x_{11} \boxplus -4 \odot x_{12} \boxplus -5 \odot x_{13}$$

$$f_2 = x_{21} \boxplus -1 \odot x_{22} \boxplus -3 \odot x_{23}$$

$$f_3 = x_{31} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{32} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{33}$$

Then we look at the product of the three polynomials. We can use Lemma 24 to draw the arrangement \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} .

$$\begin{aligned}
F_V(x_{11}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{21}, x_{22}, x_{23}, x_{31}, x_{32}, x_{33}) &= f_1 \odot f_2 \odot f_3 \\
&= (x_{11} \boxplus -4 \odot x_{12} \boxplus -5 \odot x_{13}) \odot (x_{21} \boxplus -1 \odot x_{22} \boxplus -3 \odot x_{23}) \\
&\odot (x_{31} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{32} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{33}) \\
&= x_{11}x_{21}x_{31} \boxplus -1 \odot x_{11}x_{22}x_{31} \boxplus -3 \odot x_{11}x_{23}x_{31} \boxplus -4 \odot x_{12}x_{21}x_{31} \boxplus -5 \odot x_{12}x_{22}x_{31} \\
&\boxplus -7 \odot x_{12}x_{23}x_{31} \boxplus -5 \odot x_{13}x_{21}x_{31} \boxplus -6 \odot x_{13}x_{22}x_{31} \boxplus -8 \odot x_{13}x_{23}x_{31} \\
&\boxplus -2 \odot x_{11}x_{21}x_{32} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{11}x_{21}x_{32} \boxplus -3 \odot x_{11}x_{22}x_{32} \boxplus -5 \odot x_{11}x_{23}x_{32} \\
&\boxplus -6 \odot x_{12}x_{21}x_{32} \boxplus -7 \odot x_{12}x_{22}x_{32} \boxplus -9 \odot x_{12}x_{23}x_{32} \boxplus -7 \odot x_{13}x_{21}x_{32} \\
&\boxplus -8 \odot x_{13}x_{22}x_{32} \boxplus -10 \odot x_{13}x_{23}x_{32} \boxplus -2 \odot x_{11}x_{21}x_{33} \boxplus -3 \odot x_{11}x_{22}x_{33} \\
&\boxplus -5 \odot x_{11}x_{23}x_{33} \boxplus -6 \odot x_{12}x_{21}x_{33} \boxplus -7 \odot x_{12}x_{22}x_{33} \boxplus -9 \odot x_{12}x_{23}x_{33} \\
&\boxplus -7 \odot x_{13}x_{21}x_{33} \boxplus -8 \odot x_{13}x_{22}x_{33} \boxplus -10 \odot x_{13}x_{23}x_{33}
\end{aligned}$$

The tropical hypersurface of this polynomial lives in a high dimensional space like with the envelope $\mathcal{E}(V)$ or the polyhedron $\mathcal{P}(V)$ that we worked with in the previous two subsections. Note now that we have three ways of labelling a face/region. The type, the covector graph, and the exponent vector of the monomial. To see the hypersurface in the 2-tropical torus \mathbb{TA}^2 we

Figure 28

substitute y_j in place of x_{ij} for each i in $[n]$, as discussed in Remark 61.

$$\begin{aligned}
F_V(y_1, y_2, y_3) &= y_1^3 \boxplus -7 \odot y_1^2 y_2 \boxplus -10 \odot y_1^2 y_3 \boxplus -14 \odot y_1 y_2^2 \\
&\boxplus -20 \odot y_1 y_3^2 \boxplus -24 \odot y_1 y_2 y_3 \boxplus -7 \odot y_2^3 \\
&\boxplus -24 \odot y_2^2 y_3 \boxplus -27 \odot y_2 y_3^3 \boxplus -10 \odot y_3^3.
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

This yields the max tropical hyperplane arrangement in Figure 29.

Figure 30 below shows an example of a covector decomposition in \mathbb{TA}^3 , note that there is just one bounded cell which was seen in Figure 9a above. This is an example of a three dimensional polytrope whose tropical vertices are in tropical general position. In other words this polytrope has the maximal number of pseudovertrices a polytrope can have in \mathbb{TA}^3 . As before we have that the red faces represent unbounded directions.

Figure 29: The max tropical hyperplanes are marked. The region labelled by the example covector in Figure 28 is given a different colour.

The polynomial in the y_j variables seen in (21) gives the same decomposition of the $d - 1$ -tropical torus as the polynomial in the x_{ij} variables. This suggests that we can label our decomposition with labels containing less information.

Definition 64. For a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, we associate to it the polynomial $F_V(y_1, \dots, y_d)$ and the max tropical hyperplane arrangement \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} . We have $\mathcal{T}(F_V) = \mathcal{A}_V^{\max}$. Fix a point $x \in (\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)} \setminus \mathcal{A}_V^{\max})$ in the interior of a maximal dimensional cell of the decomposition induced by V . The maximal dimensional cell that contains x is defined by a monomial of F_V , the one that attains the maximum. We define the *coarse type* or *monomial label* or *right degree vector* of x as a d -tuple $\mathbf{t}_V(x)$ of integers that describes the exponent vector of that monomial. We extend this definition to any point of $x \in \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ by taking the lowest common multiple of the monomials that attain the maximum at x .

By our previous discussion we see that the exponent vector of the monomial associated to x is the same as the right degree incidence vector of the bipartite covector graph.

Example 65. We consider the same $F_V(y_1, y_2, y_3)$ as in Example 63. The coarse type of a point found in the interior of the blue region is $\mathbf{t}_V(x) = (3, 0, 0)$. We make the same diagram as Figure 28, this time for the top right tropical vertex, which was the apex of the red max tropical hyperplane in Figure 29.

Coarse types seem to offer the same labelling properties as fine types/covector graphs, but with less information, although it is not yet clear how true that is. The following result shows that coarse types are worth further study. First note that the coarse types of the full dimensional cells are compositions of n into d parts. In particular, the number of arcs in the covector graph is the same for each covector graph that describes a full dimensional cell.

Figure 30

Theorem 66. (Theorem 2.9, [DJS12]) For a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and its corresponding max tropical hyperplane arrangement \mathcal{A}_V^{\max} , t_V seen as a map from the set of maximal dimensional cells of the decomposition C_V to the set of compositions of n into d parts is injective. Moreover, if the points V are in tropical generic position then the map t_V is bijective.

The proof uses a combinatorial argument about the monomials that attain the maximum. Also see Proposition 4.2 of [DJS12] for a reformulation of the same statement.

In that same source it is shown that this theorem does not hold for cells of C_V of any dimension. A counter example to cells of dimension one is shown. Specifically it is shown that two one dimensional cells have the same coarse type. See the discussion after Theorem 2.9 in [DJS12]. Despite this shortcoming, coarse types can still be useful especially for vertices, for example via the following result.

Figure 31: The three descriptions of the vertex v_{red} in Figure 29 that is the apex of the red max tropical hyperplane. These three descriptions yield the coarse type $\mathbf{t}_V(v_{red}) = (1, 2, 2)$

Theorem 67. (Theorem 28, [Loh20]) For a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ in tropically generic position and C_V its covector decomposition. We have that each 0-dimensional cell in C_V has a unique coarse type.

In other words, when discussing a point configuration V in tropically generic position, the covector graph G of any vertex of C_V is described uniquely by its right degree vector. The proof in the source provided uses the full dimensional cells of the regular subdivision of the product of simplices $\Delta_{n-1} \times \Delta_{d-1}$ dual to the covector decomposition C_V . In the tropically generic case, this regular subdivision is a triangulation, as we discussed in subsection 1.5. Historically speaking, the argument there is an old one, using graph theoretic ideas that come from combinatorial theory of triangulations. We continue this discussion with a focus on polytropes in subsection 4.2.

The flow chart in Figure 25 summarizes the contents of this section so far.

3.4 Polytropes Revisited

Polytropes, defined in subsection 1.3, are tropical polytopes that are also convex in the ordinary sense. The results about point configurations in the previous subsections and the construction of weighted digraph polyhedra in section 2 show that polytropes are very central in the tropical convexity world.

Recall, Theorem 14 gives us that polytropes are tropical simplices. This means that a polytrope $P \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ will have a generating set of d tropical vertices $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$. Thus, we can use V as a $d \times d$ matrix to the polytrope P as the weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V)$. In other words V will be the tight Kleene star description that we discussed in subsection 2.

We can reverse this construction. Start with a bounded weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(W) \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, we have

$$Q(W) = Q(W^*) = \text{tconv}(W^*)$$

is a polytrope. Recall that the union of bounded cells of the covector decomposition C_V induced by a point configuration V give us $\text{tconv}(V)$. This implies that we can see tropical polytropes

as complexes of polytropes, this is referred to by some authors as a tropical triangulation of a tropical polytope.

Thus when a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ gives a polytrope $P = \text{tconv}(V)$ that implies there is only one bounded cell in the corresponding covector decomposition C_V . In this case we refer to the type of P as the *base type* or the *base covector graph* of C_V .

The following results give us upper bounds on the number of pseudovertrices and the number of facets a polytrope can have.

Proposition 68. (*Proposition 15, [JK10]*) *A polytrope in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ has at most $d(d-1)$ ordinary facets. This bound is sharp.*

The proof uses root systems of type A_{d-1} , which is the point of view of [LP07], where polytropes are referred to as alcoved polytopes. In section 3 of [JK10] a class of polytropes that attains the maximum number of facets is constructed.

Proposition 69. (*Proposition 19, [DS04]*) *A polytrope in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ has at most $\binom{2(d-1)}{d-1}$ pseudovertrices. This bound is sharp.*

The proof of the above result uses Theorem 2.3 (2) of [GGP97]. In section 4 of [JK10], a class of polytropes that attain the upper bound is constructed. For full dimensional polytropes in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ we have a lower bound of d on the number of pseudovertrices. This lower bound is attained by the following polytrope, which is also an ordinary simplex.

$$P = \text{tconv}(0, e_1, e_1 + e_2, \dots, e_1 + \dots + e_{d-1}).$$

Where the e_i 's are the standard basis vectors of $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ viewed in $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$.

4 Vertices of Polytropes

For applications to optimization, we would like to better understand how the pieces of tropical convexity fit together when discussing vertices and faces. In this section, we discuss different ways of describing the vertices of a polytrope. Given a polytrope $P \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, we can see it as the base cell of the covector decomposition C_V induced by the point configuration V (which is the set of its tropical vertices). We can also see P as a bounded weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V)$, as discussed in subsection 3.4. A vertex v of P has an inequality description which can be described by a spanning tree of the digraph $\Gamma(V)$. As a cell of the covector decomposition, the vertex v has a covector graph describing it. In subsection 4.1, and specifically in Proposition 71, we prove the relationship between these different descriptions.

In the second half of subsection 3.3, we introduced coarse types. Coarse types are smaller than covector graphs as data structures. Thus a reduction of complexity motivates us to see how useful coarse vertices are. While we know that coarse types do not give unique labels to all cells of a covector decomposition, Theorem 67 shows that they may be natural labels for the vertices. In subsection 4.2 we formalize and discuss this question.

The vertices of the polytrope P have spanning trees describing them, since a vertex of any polytope in $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ can be described by the intersection of $d - 1$ hyperplanes. In subsection 4.3 we discuss some examples at how the spanning trees of neighbouring vertices of P look in relation to one and other. Being able to run the simplex algorithm more efficiently on polytropes motivates this discussion. Through our results in subsection 4.1, we can relate coarse types to the spanning trees of the vertices.

4.1 Subgraphs and Covector Graphs

In this subsection we show our contribution of making the connection between the two graphical descriptions of faces of a polytrope. One comes from the weighted digraph, in other words the inequality description, the other comes from the covector graph describing a cell in the covector decomposition.

Again we consider a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ where $v_i = (v_{i1}, \dots, v_{id})$. We also let V represent an $n \times d$ matrix, where the rows are the points. We consider V to be such that the tropical polytope $P = \text{tconv}(V)$ is convex in the ordinary sense, so P is a polytrope. We also assume V to be minimal in the sense that V contains only the tropical vertices of P . We further assume that P is full dimensional which, by Theorem 14, tells us that P has d tropical vertices. So V is a $d \times d$ matrix. It will be useful to be able to distinguish the indices of the points and the indices of the dimension, so we mark the points with indexing set $[d]$ and the dimension with $[d']$.

Since V is a square matrix, we are now able to describe P as a weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V)$, which is the ordinary polyhedral inequality description of P . We can also write $Q(W)$, where $W^* = V$, see subsection 3.4 for details. Another way to describe P is as the projection

of a face of the high dimensional polyhedron $\mathcal{E}(V) \subset \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^{d'}$, which we called the envelope of V in subsection 2.2. This placed P as a bounded cell, in fact as the only bounded cell, of the polyhedral decomposition C_V of the tropical torus $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{A}^{(d-1)}$. Recall that we referred to the type of P as the base type of the covector decomposition, see section 3.4. We let H be the base type or the base covector graph of the covector decomposition C_V . In Figure 32(d) we have the base covector graph of our running example. By reordering the rows of V , we can always have H be the 'horizontal arcs'. This is just reordering the indices of the points of the point configuration, which has no other effect. Recall from Remark 42 that we can shift the points of V so that we have zeros along the diagonal.

Recall our notion of a subgraph of a digraph. For G a digraph on the node set N , a subgraph K of G is a digraph on the same node set N , whose arcs are a subset of the arcs of G . We write this as $K \subset G$. Unless otherwise stated we take all subgraphs as unweighted, even if the parent graph is weighted.

As we stated, there are two descriptions of our polytope P . In either description of P we have a way to describe P 's faces using subgraphs of a different parent graphs. Let F be a face of P , we recall the subgraphs that describe it.

In the inequality/weighted digraph description we have subgraphs of $\Gamma_F \subset \Gamma(W)$. Recall the matrix construction in Lemma 37, where $W\#\Gamma_F$ was a matrix such that $Q(W\#\Gamma_F) = F$. Describing the face F using a subgraph $\Gamma_F \subset \Gamma(W)$ is essentially dealing with the H -representation of P . Setting inequalities to equality is what the construction $W\#F$ formalizes. For $(i, j) \in \Gamma_F$ the inequality $x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij}$ is set to equality by setting the weight of its anti-arc to the negative of its weight $x_i - x_j \leq -w_{ij}$. This gives us the H -representation of F .

In case of redundant inequalities/arcs, we may have multiple subgraphs describing one face. This prompts a definition of a more complete object.

Definition 70. For a face of a polytope $P = Q(W)$, let the collection $\{\Gamma_F^i\}_{i \in I}$ be all subgraphs of $\Gamma(W^*)$ such that

$$Q(W\#\Gamma_F^i) = F.$$

We define the *union subgraph* of F as the subgraph of $\Gamma(W^*)$ that contains arcs of all the Γ_F^i 's

$$\bar{\Gamma}_F = \bigcup_i \Gamma_F^i.$$

Note that we still have

$$Q(W\#\bar{\Gamma}_F) = F.$$

On the other hand, in the description via the envelope, we have the covector graphs which are subgraphs of the bipartite graph $B(V)$. This bipartite digraph is complete on the parts $[d]$ and $[d']$, since take all entries to be finite. We denote the covector graph describing the face F as $B_F \subset B(V)$. In subsection 3.2 we explained how these covector graphs describe cells in the covector decomposition C_V . There, C_V came from the projection $\pi_{[d]}$ of the boundary complex of the envelope $\mathcal{E}(V) \subset \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^{d'}$. This is to say that the covector graph B_F describes the face F , a cell in the decomposition C_V , by describing its preimage $\pi_{[d]}^{-1}(F)$ in the boundary

complex of the envelope. In Lemma 44, we saw the matrix construction $V[B_F]$ that gave us $Q(V[B_F] \odot V) = F$. Note that with H as the base covector graph we have that $Q(V[H] \odot V) = P$.

Figure 32(b) shows the union subgraph and the covector graph of a vertex of our running example, introduced in Example 32. The covector graph in Figure 32(c) is a subgraph of the bipartite graph we introduced in Figure 18(a), which was the same as our running example.

Note that here the union subgraph is really made up of just one subgraph. Figure 38, in Example 72 below, shows a better example of what a union subgraph may look like when there are redundant arcs, the parent digraph is shown in Figure 35(b).

Figure 32: A vertex v of P with its union subgraph Γ_v and its covector graph B_v .

The two matrix constructions mentioned above are reflected in augmentations of the parent graphs. In Figures 33b and 34 we see how the parent graphs are changed by their respective subgraphs that we introduced in Figure 32.

These two graphical ways of describing a face F are implicitly connected via the constructions in section 2. The following proposition spells out this connection.

Proposition 71. *Consider a polytope $P = Q(W^*) = \text{tconv}(V) \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$, with vertices $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\}$. For a face F of P , let $B_F \subset B(V)$ be the covector graph of F and let $\bar{\Gamma}_F \subset \Gamma(W^*)$ be the union subgraph of F . Then we have*

$$(i, j') \in B_F \quad \text{if and only if} \quad (i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F.$$

Before reading the proof, the reader should recall Lemma 39, along with Lemma 37 and Lemma 44 recalled above, which discussed projecting weighted digraph polyhedra onto coordinate planes.

(a) $\Gamma(W\#\Gamma_V)$. The blue arcs were the ones augmented. See the original digraph in Figure 15.

(b) $\Gamma(V_W\#H)$ with H in red and the arcs added by its augmentation in blue. Note that there now exist 2-arc-paths between the nodes in right part.

Figure 33

Proof. For B_F to be the covector graph of F , that means F is equal to the weighted digraph polyhedron $Q(V[B_F] \odot V)$. Similarly we have $F = Q(V\#\Gamma_F)$. Note that this looks different than its definition in (8) since we have that V is a square matrix, so we do not need the W notation.

Suppose $(i, j') \in B_F$. We show the union subgraph contains the arc $(i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F$.

We claim that the arc (j, i) in the graph $\Gamma(V[B_F] \odot V)$ will have weight equal to $-v_{ij}$. This will come from the definition of $V[B_F]$ in (10) and an argument similar to that of the proof of Lemma 44. The colours used in the following correspond to the colouring of the arcs in Figures 33b(b) and 34.

Let H be the base covector graph of P . From Lemma 37 and Proposition 50 (iii) we have that H is a subgraph of B_F since F is a face of P . So the augmented $\Gamma(V_W\#H)$ (see the matrix below) will have the reverse arcs of all the 'horizontal' arcs, while $\Gamma(V_W\#B_F)$ will have those as well as some 'non-horizontal' arcs that go from right to left.

$$V_W\#H = \left(\begin{array}{ccc|c} & \infty_{d \times d} & & V \\ \hline v_{11} = 0 & & \infty & \\ \left(\begin{array}{ccc} & \cdot & \\ & \cdot & \\ \infty & & v_{dd} = 0 \end{array} \right) & & & \infty_{d \times d} \end{array} \right)$$

We augment the matrix representing the high dimensional envelope, $\Gamma(V_W\#H)$ like in the proof of Lemma 44. Take the two nodes i' and j' in $[d']$, the right part of $B(V)$. We have the 2-arc-path

$$i' \xrightarrow{-v_{ii}=0} i \xrightarrow{v_{ij}} j'$$

Figure 34: $\Gamma(V_W \# B_F)$ with B_F in red and the arcs added by its augmentation in blue. Note the new 2-arc-paths.

with a total weight of v_{ij} ($v_{ii} = 0$ by shifting of V). This 2-arc-path will become the arc from node i' to node j' when we project down with the map $\pi_{[d]}$ from the envelope to the tropical torus. This was detailed in Lemma 39, where projection along $\pi_{[d]}$ deletes nodes in the left part $[d]$ of $B(V)$. Since there are no other 2-arc-paths from i' to j' we are assured that the weight of the arc (i, j) will be v_{ij} . Note that the shifting of V gives us that self loops (arcs from a node i' to itself) have weight zero.

Now we look at the 2-arc-paths present in the $\Gamma(V_W \# B_F)$ case. Since $(i, j') \in B_F$, we have that the arc (j', i) has weight $-v_{ij}$ when we augment. Since B_F contains H we have that from the node j' to the node i' there will be two 2-arc-paths, note the reversal of the nodes. From H (as above) we have

$$j' \xrightarrow{-v_{jj}=0} j \xrightarrow{v_{ji}} i' \quad \text{total weight} = v_{ji},$$

and from the fact that $(i, j') \in B_F$ we have

$$j' \xrightarrow{-v_{ij}} i \xrightarrow{v_{ii}=0} i' \quad \text{total weight} = -v_{ij}.$$

Since we always assume there are no negative cycles in our digraph we have that

$$\min\{v_{ji}, -v_{ij}\} = -v_{ij}.$$

So when we project down via $\pi_{[d]}$ the arc (j, i) will have the weight $-v_{ij}$, which is equal to the negative of the weight of arc (i, j) . This sets the inequality $x_j - x_i \leq v_{ij}$ to an equality. Since

this is one of the augmentations of $\Gamma(V)$ that give rise to the face F , then $\bar{\Gamma}_F$ must also make that augmentation when we look at $V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F$. From the definition of the matrix construction $\#$ in (8) it is clear that one can reconstruct $\bar{\Gamma}_F$ from the matrix $V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F$. Hence, we have that the arc $(i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F$.

The opposite direction is easier. We start with an arc $(i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F$. We then compute the square matrix $V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F$. We can reconstruct B_F from the matrix $V[B_F]$, so we just need to find the matrix $A \in \mathbb{T}^{d \times d}$ such that

$$A \odot V = V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F.$$

To do this we simply compare $V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F$ and V . For the arc $(i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F$, the entry $(V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F)_{ji} = -v_{ij}$. Thus, we can set

$$A_{ji} = \begin{cases} -v_{ij} & (i, j) \in \bar{\Gamma}_F \\ \infty & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

Building $\bar{\Gamma}_F$ from this gives us that (i, j') is in B_F . This completes the proof. \square

The following diagram summarizes the above proof.

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} B_F & \longleftrightarrow & V[B_F] & \xrightarrow{Q(\cdot \odot V)} & F & \xleftarrow{Q(\cdot)} & V\#\bar{\Gamma}_F & \longleftrightarrow & \bar{\Gamma}_F \\ & & & & & & \downarrow & & \\ & & & & & & V[B_F] & & \end{array}$$

Example 72. We consider at a polytrope $P = Q(W) = \text{tconv}(V)$ with W and V below.

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & -1 & 3 \\ 1 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 3 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} \quad V = W^* = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & -1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & 0 & 6 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

These matrices give us the digraphs in Figure 35

We look at the covector graphs and the union subgraphs of two of its pseudovertices. We denote the tropical vertex, yellow in Figure 36 below, as v_t , and the other pseudovertex in red as v_p .

Now in Figure 37 we look at the covector graphs of vertices v_p and v_t .

Finally we see the union subgraphs of the vertices v_p and v_t . The reader can compare these to the covector graphs like in Proposition 71.

In Example 72 above we have that the tropical vertex v_t is in first position in the point configuration V , that is to say $v_1 = v_t$. We see that v_t has a union subgraph $\bar{\Gamma}_{v_t}$ which is the shortest path tree rooted at the first node. Recall the interpretation of the covector decomposition coming from max tropical hyperplanes with the points in V as the apices. This interpretation shows us that a tropical vertex will always have a covector graph like the one above as it is in all of the max sectors on its hyperplane. This was formalized in [BLM22a] as the following.

Figure 35

Figure 36: $Q(W) \subset \mathbb{TA}^3$. Here the tropical vertices are marked in yellow. With the large squares we highlight two pseudovertices, one of which is tropical.

Lemma 73. (Lemma 3.17, [BLM22a]) *The tropical vertices V of the polytope*

$$P = Q(W^*) = \text{tconv}(V)$$

are in bijection with the shortest path trees rooted at each node of the digraph $\Gamma(W^)$.*

Figure 37

(a) All the subgraphs that yield v_p . Note that not all of these are subgraphs of $\Gamma(W)$.

(b) Union subgraph of v_p .

(c) Union subgraph of v_t .

Figure 38

4.2 Coarse Types of Vertices

With an outlook to optimization in mind, we are interested in descriptions of vertices that may lower complexity/runtime of algorithms. Coarse types, defined in subsection 3.3, are less complex than covector graphs/fine types. However Theorem 67 suggests that they may still contain the information needed to label the vertices of our polytope.

Fix a polytope P with tropical vertices $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_d\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$. We would like to know if coarse types of the pseudoverties of P are unique in the case where V is not in tropically generic position.

The proof of Theorem 67 compares the number of full dimensional cells in a triangulation of the product of simplices to the number of compositions of n into d parts. There V has n points as it did before we specified to the polytope case. This argument does not work for in the nongeneric case since the coarse types different pseudoverties may not have the same sum. Therefore we cannot use the idea of counting compositions into parts. In Example 72 we have a nongeneric polytope. We can read off the coarse types of the pseudoverties v_p and v_t from

the covector graphs. Recall that the right degree vector of the covector graph is the coarse type. We have

$$\mathbf{t}_V(v_p) = (3, 1, 4, 1), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{t}_V(v_t) = (1, 2, 2, 2).$$

When summing the entries of these vectors we get 9 and 7 respectively.

Question 74. For a point configuration $V = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\} \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ and the tropical polytope $P = \text{tconv}(V)$

- (i) Are the zero dimensional cells of the covector decomposition C_V induced by V uniquely labelled by their coarse types?
- (ii) Does the above hold in the more specialized case of P being a polytope? (note here that we have $n = d$)

This question is not answered in this thesis, but some computations of large examples show that a positive answer is promising. These computations are the subject of subsection 5.2. There we discuss somethings currently lacking in software handling tropical geometry and some contributions made.

Proposition 71 gave us the connection between covector graphs and union subgraphs of faces of polytopes. This then extends over to coarse types. The coarse type read off of the union subgraph will be a d -tuple where the i^{th} entry counts how many arcs enter node i . We discuss implications of this connection in section 6.2.

4.3 Adjacent Vertices

With the discussion of the previous two subsections in mind, we turn to what the simplex algorithm could look like on polytopes. The simplex algorithm pivots from one vertex to the next until reaching a certificate of optimality. In the context of weighted graph polyhedra, the vertices are labelled by union subgraphs. A goal would be to understand what union subgraphs of adjacent vertices have in common. We have from ordinary polyhedral geometry the description of P 's vertices by spanning trees. This is because a vertex of any polytope in $\mathbb{R}^{(d-1)}$ can be described by the intersection of $d - 1$ hyperplanes. These spanning trees appear as (potentially not proper) subgraphs of the union subgraph. Recall from subsection 4.1, the union subgraph is a subgraph of the weighted digraph $\Gamma(V)$, described the polytope P as a weighted digraph polyhedron.

Once pivoting between union subgraphs/spanning trees is understood, it may be possible to understand what pivoting looks like on the coarse types. This would allow for a reduction in complexity. This subsection does not contain any results, instead we focus only on discussing structural aspects related to vertices of polytopes, their spanning trees, and the spanning tree of their adjacent vertices.

Pivoting between spanning trees has been studied as the *network simplex algorithm*, see section 11.5 of the standard [AMO93].

Figure 39: The labelling of the vertices is used in Figure 40 below.

We centre this discussion around two worked out examples. In light of Proposition 71, it is enough to draw the union subgraphs and omit the covector graphs of the vertices. In the figures we exclude the self loops of the nodes, which still appear in the coarse types of the vertices.

Example 75. We consider the polytope we introduced in Figure 9(a), which came from points in tropically generic position. The points are the rows of the following matrix

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 3 & 1 & 4 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & -5 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 & -2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In Figure 39 we show the polytope again, but now with vertices labelled. In Figure 40, we show the union subgraphs and coarse types of all the pseudoverties of this polytope.

In Example 75 all the vertices have spanning trees as union subgraphs. This is due to the the tropical vertices being in tropical generic position. Recalling Lemma 73, we see that the spanning trees of the tropical vertices are of 'rooted' type. If we look specifically at vertices 2 and 17 in Figure 39, we can see that there are two pseudoverties as breakpoint in the tropical line segment between them. In Figure 40, we see that passing from the spanning tree of vertex 2 to the spanning tree of vertex 17 amounts to switching the arcs till the root of the spanning tree is changed. This, however, is not true in general. For example vertex 0 is not on the tropical line segment of any two tropical vertices, but rather in the tropical convex hull of three tropical vertices. The next example shows further complications that arise when we consider nongeneric and nonsimple polytropes.

First, recall from Example 72 the 'redundant' arcs that were added to the weighted digraph describing the polytope. Since the polytope (which looked close to a cube) had six facets, we

Figure 40: The union subgraphs, which in this case are all spanning trees, and the coarse types of all the vertices of the polytope in Figure 39 and Example 75. The tropical vertices are given blue squares. Self loops are omitted.

Figure 41: The labelling of the vertices is used in Figure 42 below.

would only need a weighted digraph with six arcs to describe it. However, the union subgraph is a subgraph of the complete digraph associated to the Kleene star matrix. In the next example we distinguish the arcs in the union subgraphs which are 'redundant'. In Figure 42 those arcs are marked in red.

It may be beneficial, from a complexity point of view, to consider the vertex describing spanning trees that only contain 'non-redundant' arcs.

Example 76. To contrast with the previous example, we consider the polytrope we introduced in Figure 9(b), which is not simple and came from points not in tropically generic position. The points are the rows of the following matrix

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & -3 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & -1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In Figure 41 we show the polytrope again, but now with vertices labelled. In Figure 42, we show the union subgraphs and coarse types of all the pseudovertrices of this polytrope.

As above, we look at two tropical vertices and the breakpoints of the tropical line segment between them. Tropical vertices 4 and 7 have the pseudoververtex 0 between them. Also as above we can go from the union graph of vertex 4 to the union graph of vertex 7 by swapping two arcs. After one of the swaps we end up at vertex 0.

We cannot be too quick to discard the redundant arcs in the union subgraphs, since then we

Figure 42: The union subgraphs and the coarse types of all the vertices of the polytope in Figure 41 and Example 76. The tropical vertices are given blue squares. Self loops are omitted. Arcs that comes from the concatenation of two other arcs are shown in red.

will lose the connection spelled out in Proposition 71. Lemma 73 still holds true, as we can find a rooted spanning tree as a subgraph of every tropical vertex's union graph, but some of these rooted spanning trees use redundant arcs.

Vertex 2 is where the polytrope of Example 76 is nonsimple. We can see in Figure 42, vertex 2's union graph has four arcs, non of which are redundant. While we can represent vertex 2 with just three of these arcs, it is not clear which spanning tree within the union graph is the natural choice and how it will relate to its neighbouring vertices and the spanning trees representing them.

5 Computations in Tropical Convexity

In this thesis we explored graph theoretic, combinatorial, and polyhedral aspects of tropical convexity. There are many choices of mathematical software exploring these branches of math. Tropical geometry is a relatively new field and the software in this area is still catching up and being developed. The visualizations and computations throughout this thesis were computed using the OSCAR Computer Algebra System [OSC24] and the software polymake [GJ00] within it. OSCAR is a recent project that is free and open source, it is also open to contributions. In this section, we show how to compute visualizations that can be very helpful to get a feeling for the geometry. We also explain some functions needed for the computations mentioned in subsection 4.2. These functions have been reviewed by the OSCAR team and merged into the code base there. We mark which functions have been merged into OSCAR and whether they are accessible to users or not. Writing these functions and discussing them with the OSCAR team has prompted a larger project regarding the implementation of tropical convexity. We make some comments on this project here, but it lies outside the scope of this thesis.

Polymake uses the perl programming language and predates OSCAR, which uses Julia. In fact one of the main reasons OSCAR exists is to integrate polymake and other computer algebra system to be used together in Julia. This is a work in progress and not everything in polymake is accessible in OSCAR. We show some ways to move between the two systems. The reader can consult the OSCAR and polymake websites for helpful tutorials, and also the OSCAR textbook (which is not yet published at the time of writing) [DEF⁺24].

5.1 Visualizations

Polymake uses the perl language and is useful for computations in tropical convexity. We specifically show its uses for computing tropical convex hulls and visualizations. OSCAR proves to be much more user friendly for anything polynomial related or writing logic and functions.

All computations done inside a Julia shell. Once we start "using OSCAR" we can go to a polymake shell. To be clear, to go from line 2 to line 3 in Listing 1 below, one types in `$`. We start with computing the polytrope that was our running example, the hexagon seen in Figure 15c.

The last two lines allow us to view the polytrope and then save a customizable tikz file of the picture, see [Tan]. Some diagrams are easier to deal with as `.svg` files. For this we use the free and open source software Inkscape. We can also visualize the covector subdivision induced by this point configuration, as well as the Hasse diagram of its face poset. Reading the output of line 2 in the block requires us to know polymake's labelling of the pseudovertrices of the polytrope. We print of the pseudovertrices and then confirm which ones are our tropical vertices. Note that `$HEX->VERTICES` returns the minimal generating set of tropical vertices. To get the original input for the tropical convex hull one can use `$HEX->POINTS;`. Line 1 and 2 in Listing 2 give us Figure 26.

```

1 julia> using Oscar
2 julia>
3 common>
4 common> application "tropical";
5 tropical> $HEX = new Polytope<Min>(POINTS
    ↪ =>[[0,4,5],[0,1,3],[0,2,2]]);
6 tropical> $HEX->VISUAL;
7 tropical> tikz($HEX->VISUAL, File=>"HEX.tikz");

```

Listing 1: The polymake code that generated the tropical polytopes in Figure 15c.

```

1 tropical> $HEX->VISUAL_SUBDIVISION;
2 tropical> svg($HEX->POLYTOPE_COVECTOR_DECOMPOSITION->VISUAL);
3 tropical> print(rows_labeled($HEX->VERTICES));
4 0:0 4 5
5 1:0 1 3
6 2:0 2 2
7 tropical> print(rows_labeled($HEX->PSEUDOVERTICES));
8 0:0 0 -1 0
9 1:0 0 1 1
10 2:0 0 0 -1
11 3:1 0 1 2
12 4:1 0 4 4
13 . . .

```

Listing 2: Covector decomposition and the Hasse diagram of its face poset. Both seen in Figure 26

Since polytopes are ordinarily convex we can also use the `polytope` application in `polymake` to explore their properties. This requires us to create an object of a different type. Note that we would have to add an x_0 to the inequalities in Listing 3 and then increase all indices by 1 in order to make the inequality description look like our usual weighted digraph polyhedron.

To generate examples like Example 30 we need to work with tropical polynomials, their hyper-surfaces, and their dual subdivisions. To do this completely in `polymake` is difficult as one will have to use Perl. It is possible to do almost all the work in Julia and then pass some information over to the `polymake` shell to get a visualization of the subdivision. This passing over is what the `Polymake.Shell` does in line 9 of Listing 5. First we get the tropical polynomial ready in Listing 4.

```

1 tropical > $ORDINARY_HEX = new polytope::Polytope(POINTS=>$
    ↪ HEX->PSEUDOVERTICES->minor([3,4,5,6,7,8],~[1]));
2 tropical > print_constraints($ORDINARY_HEX);
3 Facets:
4 0: x1 >= 1
5 1: x2 >= 2
6 2: x1 - x2 >= -2
7 3: -x1 + x2 >= 0
8 4: -x1 >= -4
9 5: -x2 >= -5
10
11 tropical > print(rows_labeled($ORDINARY_HEX->VERTICES));
12 0:1 1 2
13 1:1 4 4
14 2:1 3 5
15 3:1 4 5
16 4:1 1 3
17 5:1 2 2
18
19 tropical > print(rows_labeled($ORDINARY_HEX->LATTICE_POINTS))
    ↪ ;
20 0:1 1 2
21 1:1 1 3
22 2:1 2 2
23 3:1 2 3
24 4:1 2 4
25 . . .

```

Listing 3: We get the Polytope type object of our polytrope. This allows us to access all the its properties as a polytope. We show how to its H -description, its vertices as an ordinary polytope, and the lattice points in it.

```

1 julia> T_max = tropical_semiring(max)
2 Max tropical semiring
3 julia> S, (t,x,y)=T_max["t", "x", "y"];
4 julia> F_1 = t + x + y
5 t + x + y
6 julia> F_2 = t + -3x + -1y
7 t + (-3)*x + (-1)*y
8 julia> F_3 = t + -2x + 1y
9 t + (-2)*x + (1)*y
10 julia> F_4 = t + 1x + -2y
11 t + (1)*x + (-2)*y
12 julia> F_V = F_1 * F_2 * F_3 * F_4
13 t^4 + (1)*t^3*x + (1)*t^2*x^2 + (-1)*t*x^3 + (-4)*x^4 + (1)*t
    ↪ ^3*y + (2)*t^2*x*y + (2)*t*x^2*y + (-1)*x^3*y + (1)*t
    ↪ ^2*y^2 + (2)*t*x*y^2 + (1)*x^2*y^2 + t*y^3 + (1)*x*y^3
    ↪ + (-2)*y^4
14 julia> T_F_V = tropical_hypersurface(F_V)
15 Max tropical hypersurface
16 julia> S_F_V = dual_subdivision(T_F_V)
17 type: Hypersurface<Max>
18 COEFFICIENTS
19 0 1 1 -1 -4 1 2 2 -1 1 2 1 0 1 -2
20 MONOMIALS
21 0 4 0 0
22 0 3 1 0
23 0 2 2 0
24 0 1 3 0
25 0 0 4 0
26 0 3 0 1
27 0 2 1 1
28 . . .

```

Listing 4: We define a polynomial, and compute its tropical hypersurface and dual subdivision. This is seen in Example 30.

```

1 julia> M_F = S_F_V.MONOMIALS
2 pm::Matrix{Long}
3 0 4 0 0
4 0 3 1 0
5 . . .
6 julia> for i in 1:nrows(M_F)
7 M_F[i,1] += 1
8 end
9 julia> Polymake.Shell.M_F = M_F
10 pm::Matrix{Long}
11 1 4 0 0
12 1 3 1 0
13 . . .
14 julia> Polymake.Shell.C_F = [0, -1, -1, 1, 4, -1, -2, -2, 1,
    ↪ -1, -2, -1, 0, -1, 2]
15 15-element Vector{Int64}:
16 0
17 -1
18 . . .
19 fan > $S_F_V = new SubdivisionOfPoints(POINTS=>$M_F,WEIGHTS
    ↪ =>$C_F);
20 fan > $S_F_V->VISUAL;
21 fan > tikz($S_F_V->VISUAL(VertexLabels=>"hidden"), File=>"
    ↪ F_dual_subdiv");
22 julia> F_V(0,x,y)
23 (-4)*x^4 + (-1)*x^3*y + (1)*x^2*y^2 + (1)*x*y^3 + (-2)*y^4 +
    ↪ (-1)*x^3 + (2)*x^2*y + (2)*x*y^2 + y^3 + (1)*x^2 + (2)*
    ↪ x*y + (1)*y^2 + (1)*x + (1)*y + (0)
24 julia> S,(x,y)=T_max["x","y"];
25 julia> F_V = (-4)*x^4 + (-1)*x^3*y + (1)*x^2*y^2 + (1)*x*y^3
    ↪ + (-2)*y^4 + (-1)*x^3 + (2)*x^2*y + (2)*x*y^2 + y^3 +
    ↪ (1)*x^2 + (2)*x*y + (1)*y^2 + (1)*x + (1)*y + (0)
26 julia> visualize(tropical_hypersurface(F_V))

```

Listing 5: Here we go from Julia to polymake to get the visualization of the dual subdivision of the product polynomial.

5.2 Computations in OSCAR

In order to get a hint towards Question 74, we compute some examples. We want to see if uniqueness holds for the coarse types of the vertices of a covector decomposition in the nongeneric case. For this, we needed to write functions that can distinguish when a point configuration:

- (a) is in tropically generic/nongeneric position;
- (b) defines a polytrope when we look at $tconv(V)$.

Point (a) was solved by the function in Listing 6. Point (b) prompted a conversation with the OSCAR developer team about the implementation of tropical convexity in OSCAR. A 'band-aid' solution that returns whether $tconv(V)$ is a polytrope or not is in Listing 8. The implementation of tropical convexity is (at the time of writing) underway and is outside the scope of this thesis. For that reason we only include a few comments in subsection 6.2.

Recall from subsection 1.5 that a point configuration V is in tropically generic position if all the maximal minors of V seen as a matrix are tropically regular. For this we use the polymake function `tsgn` which is the sign of the tropical determinant defined in Definition 31. This is implemented as the function `is_tropically_generic` in Listing 6.

```
1 function is_tropically_generic(A::MatrixElem{<:
  ↪ TropicalSemiringElem})
2   #=Helper function=#
3   function helper(A,C,B)
4     for b in subsets(C,B)
5       Polymake.tropical.tsgn(A[b,:]) == 0 && return
  ↪ false
6     end
7     return true
8   end
9   nca = ncols(A)
10  nra = nrows(A)
11  if nca == nra
12    return Polymake.tropical.tsgn(A) != 0
13  elseif nra>nca
14    return helper(A,nra,nca)
15  else
16    return helper(transpose(A),nca,nra)
17  end
18 end
```

Listing 6: A function in OSCAR checking whether a point configuration is in tropically generic position.

The function in Listing 7 outputs whether for a point configuration $V \subset \mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ the tropical convex hull $tconv(V) = P$ is a polytrope. This prompted a conversation with the OSCAR team about how there is no tropical polytope class that this function can be a method of. The solution of simply wrapping the tropical polytope type in polymake was not satisfactory as there is research interest in allowing for infinity to be an entry in the points of V . In other words, tropical polytopes should live in tropical projective space $\mathbb{TP}^{(d-1)}$, and not only in the tropical torus $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$ as we have been considering.

For details regarding tropical convexity in tropical projective space $\mathbb{TP}^{(d-1)}$ see section 5.1 of [Jos21]. There, the boundary of tropical projective space and its induced decomposition are studied.

The function `is_polytrope` also prompted the creation of some wrapper classes in OSCAR so that a user can move between Julia (OSCAR) and polymake more easily. The function `do_rows_form_polytrope` in Listing 8 is the same as `is_polytrope` just without the somewhat fragile polymake shell code. We include both since the technique used in Listing 7 may be useful when one needs to access polymake through Julia.

Remark 77. While the function `do_rows_form_polytrope` works, it is somewhat costly. It works by finding all the types of the covector decomposition C_V induced by V , and then returning `true` if there is only one such cell. We can tell which types yield bounded cells by Proposition 50 (ii). A more efficient algorithm would be to use the discussion in subsection 3.4 where we noted that for polytopes, $Q(V) = tconv(V)$. In particular, after determining the tropical vertices, we see if the resulting matrix is a Kleene star. This can be done with a shortest path computation which would be more efficient.

With these tools at hand we define a function that allows us to test the result in Question 74. In Listing 9 we define a helper function. We put together all the functions in Listing 10, and show some tests in Listing 11.

```

1 function is_polytrope (A::MatrixElem{<:TropicalSemiringElem})
2     #=Convert the matrix of tropical numbers into matrix of
3         ↪ rational numbers in to pass it into polymake's
4         ↪ tropical convex hull function =#
5     ncA = ncols(A)
6     nrA = nrows(A)
7     QQA = zero_matrix(QQ,nrA,ncA)
8     for i in 1:nrA
9         for j in 1:ncA
10            iszero(A[i,j]) && return false
11            QQA[i,j] += QQ(A[i,j])
12        end
13    end
14    #Compute the tropical convex hull
15    tempP = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)} (POINTS=
16        ↪ QQA)
17    #=Compute the tropical convex hull again, this time with
18    the minimal generating set of vertices of tropical
19        ↪ polytope=#
20    P = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)} (POINTS=
21        ↪ tempP.VERTICES)
22    pPMCV = P.POLYTOPE_MAXIMAL_COVECTORS
23    Polymake.Shell.CV = pPMCV
24    Polymake.shell_execute(raw"""$tmp = $CV->size;""")
25    return Polymake.Shell.tmp == 1
26 end

```

Listing 7: This function checks if a tropical polytope is ordinarily convex and hence a polytrope. This is an early version of the function and was not merged. Note the interaction between OSCAR and polymake in lines 16 - 19

```

1 function do_rows_form_polytrope(A::MatrixElem{<:
  ↪ TropicalSemiringElem})
2   #=Convert the matrix of tropical numbers into matrix of
  ↪ rational numbers in to pass it into polymake's
  ↪ tropical convex hull function =#
3   . . .
4   #Compute the tropical convex hull
5   tempP = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)}(POINTS=
  ↪ QQA)
6   #=Compute the tropical convex hull again, this time with
7   the minimal generating set of vertices of tropical
  ↪ polytope=#
8   P = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)}(POINTS=
  ↪ tempP.VERTICES)
9   return length(P.POLYTOPE_MAXIMAL_COVECTORS) == 1
10 end

```

Listing 8: This function has been merged into OSCAR, but is only accessible in the developer version. Line 3 is just lines 3-11 of the previous listing.

```

1 function uniqueness_of_coarse_types(M)
2   count = 0
3   for i in 1:nrows(C_types)
4     for j in i+1:nrows(C_types)
5       if C_types[j,:] == C_types[i,:]
6         count += 1
7       end
8     end
9   end
10  return "Number of pairs of coarse types that are equal is
  ↪ : " * string(count)
11 end

```

Listing 9: A simple helper function checking the uniqueness of a coarse type.

```

1 function test_an_example(A::MatrixElem{<:TropicalSemiringElem
  ↪ })
2   #Compute the tropical convex hull to check if a polytrope
3   ncA = ncols(A)
4   nrA = nrows(A)
5   QQA = zero_matrix(QQ,nrA,ncA)
6   for i in 1:nrA
7     for j in 1:ncA
8       if iszero(A[i,j])
9         return "Cannot test infinity"
10      else
11        QQA[i,j] += QQ(A[i,j])
12      end
13    end
14  end
15  if convention(A) == min
16    A_opp = matrix(tropical_semiring(max),QQA)
17  else
18    A_opp = matrix(tropical_semiring(min),QQA)
19  end
20  #Check if in tropically generic position
21  println("A in tropically generic position:" * string(
  ↪ is_tropically_generic(A_opp)))
22  full_P = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)}(POINTS
  ↪ =QQA)
23  P = Polymake.tropical.Polytope{convention(A)}(POINTS=
  ↪ full_P.VERTICES)
24  #Check if in points give a polytrope
25  println("The rows of A define a polytrope:" * string(
  ↪ length(P.POLYTOPE_MAXIMAL_COVECTORS) == 1))
26  #Compute the coarse types of the pseudovertrices
27  C_types = full_P.PSEUDOVERTEX_COARSE_COVECTORS
28  println("Number of Pseudovertrices: " * string(nrows(
  ↪ C_types)))
29  println(uniqueness_of_coarse_types(C_types))
30 end

```

Listing 10: Note that we have to change the convention of the tropical numbers before checking whether they are in tropically generic position. This is mentioned in section 3.3 where we take the max hyperplane arrangement along with the min tropical convex hull.

```

1 julia> M_3 = matrix(tropical_semiring(), [0 1 -1 3; 0 -1 -1 3;
      ↪ 0 1 -3 3; 0 1 -1 0])
2 [(0)      (1)      (-1)      (3)]
3 . . .
4 julia> test_an_example(M_3)
5 A in tropically generic position: false
6 The rows of A define a polytrope: true
7 Number of Pseudovertrices: 12
8 Number of pairs of coarse types that are equal is: 0
9
10 julia> M_4 = matrix(tropical_semiring(), [0 3 1 4; 0 -1 -1 3;
      ↪ 0 1 -5 1; 0 2 -2 0])
11 [(0)      (3)      (1)      (4)]
12 . . .
13 julia> test_an_example(M_4)
14 A in tropically generic position: true
15 The rows of A define a polytrope: true
16 Number of Pseudovertrices: 24
17 Number of pairs of coarse types that are equal is: 0
18
19 julia> M_5 = matrix(tropical_semiring(), [0 3 1 4; 0 -1 -1 3;
      ↪ 0 1 -5 1; 0 2 -2 0; 0 0 -3 2])
20 [(0)      (3)      (1)      (4)]
21 . . .
22 julia> test_an_example(M_5)
23 A in tropically generic position: true
24 The rows of A define a polytrope: true
25 Number of Pseudovertrices: 39
26 Number of pairs of coarse types that are equal is: 0
27
28 julia> M_6 = matrix(tropical_semiring(), [0 3 2 5 -1 2 0; 0
      ↪ -1 -1 3 0 3 7; 0 1 -5 1 3 2 -2; 0 2 -2 0 5 -1 1; 0 1 1
      ↪ 1 -5 11 12])
29 [(0)      (3)      (2)      (5)      (-1)      (2)      (0)]
30 . . .
31 julia> test_an_example(M_6)
32 A in tropically generic position: false
33 The rows of A define a polytrope: false
34 Number of Pseudovertrices: 129
35 Number of pairs of coarse types that are equal is: 0

```

Listing 11: Here we test a few different examples. Note that `M_3` defines the polytrope in Example 72 and `M_4` defines the polytrope in Figure 9(a).

6 Connection to Optimization and Further Questions

With \min or \max as operations of the tropical semiring one can guess that tropical geometry has connections to optimization. We already saw examples above: the computation of the Kleene star being similar to the Bellman-Ford algorithm in Remark 34, and finding the \min/\max permutation in the computation of the tropical determinant is the same as solving the linear assignment problem in Remark 28. In this section, we mention an application of tropical convexity, specifically of polytropes, to a general class of optimization problems, and then specifically to a problem from public transport optimization. We then discuss further questions that may be useful for optimization problems. For background knowledge about linear and integer programming see [AMO93].

6.1 Min Cost Flow and Periodic Timetables

We discuss an application of tropical convexity, and structural results about polytropes, to combinatorial optimization problems. First, we make a connection to a general class of problems, namely minimum cost flow duality, then, more specifically, to optimizing the timetable of a public transport network. This, in part, was motivation for our interest in the vertices of polytropes and their descriptions.

Minimum cost flow problems are very popular in the literature: a search of "min cost flow" on the arxiv yields hundreds of applications. It is often useful to consider the dual linear program, where one must find feasible *node potentials*. For background on linear programming, and more specifically min cost duality, see section 9.4 of the standard reference [AMO93].

We work in \mathbb{R}^d with coordinates (x_1, \dots, x_d) , and we fix a weighted digraph G with node set $[d]$. In the context of min cost flow duality we have inequalities of the form

$$x_j - x_i \leq w_{ij} \quad (i, j) \in G. \quad (22)$$

These are precisely the types of inequality systems that describe weighted digraph polyhedra, and polytropes in the bounded case. We see these types of inequality systems in optimization problems in current work, for an example see [Kr05].

The simplex algorithm has been applied to min cost flow problems as the network simplex algorithm. Here one pivots between spanning trees coming from the directed graph G , see chapter 11 of [AMO93]. The idea of pivoting between spanning trees of adjacent vertices of a polytrope was discussed in subsection 4.3.

In public transport optimization, the timetable that the system operates on is of great significance. The standard model used to solve for a feasible periodic timetable is the *Periodic Event Scheduling Problem* (PESP), which was first introduced in [SU89]. Finding a feasible timetable is an NP-hard problem. Nowadays, the prevailing approach of solving PESP instances exactly is mixed integer programming. The mixed integer program (MIP) that formulates the PESP contains inequalities roughly in the form of (22). This is not a coincidence as the public transport network is modelled by a digraph. This shows that the PESP is strongly related to min

cost flow duality. This application/connection is explained nicely in [FO22]. See section 2 of [BLM22a] for a quick introduction to the PESP and its MIP formulation.

In section 3 of [BLM22a], weighted digraph polyhedra are introduced as solution spaces of feasible timetables. Due to the periodicity constraint on the timetables, these polytopes live in a torus. The authors of [BLM22a] continued this line of research in [BLM22b]. There, a heuristic called the tropical neighbourhood search was developed.

6.2 Outlook

In this subsection, we discuss further structural results that would be interesting and useful to both the theory of tropical convexity and to an application in optimization.

First, there is the matter of answering Question 74 about the uniqueness of coarse types of pseudovertrices of a polytrope or just the vertices of the covector decomposition in the non tropically generic case. Our computations in 5.2 show that it is likely that the question has a positive answer.

Lemma 73 from [BLM22a] suggests the possibility of structural results concerning the union subgraph $\bar{\Gamma}_v$ of a vertex v of a polytrope P that we introduced in subsection 4.1. For applications to optimization we are interested in the spanning trees found in $\bar{\Gamma}_v$ that describe v , as discussed in subsection 4.3. In the generic case, examples show that these spanning trees may have a *non-crossing* property. For the definition of and details concerning non-crossing spanning trees see [GGP97] or [SW09].

The uniqueness of coarse types may allow one to obtain the spanning tree of a vertex from its coarse type. The union subgraph $\bar{\Gamma}_v$ of a vertex of P can have many spanning trees in it, especially in the non generic case. We could then ask if one can extract a spanning tree with the non-crossing property from $\bar{\Gamma}_v$. A priori, coarse types have less information than spanning trees, as they only record how many arcs enter each node. However, with some structural properties confining the shape that these spanning tree can take, it may be possible to construct the spanning tree from the coarse type alone.

One can use these results to improve complexity of the simplex algorithm running on a polytrope. In the generic case, pivoting can be done simply by switching the direction of an arc in the spanning tree description of a vertex. With a strong connection between coarse types and spanning trees, one can observe the behaviour of the coarse types of the vertices while pivoting and whether that would help lower complexity due to coarse types being a simpler data type.

Finally, as mentioned in subsection 5.2, there is still work to be done towards the implementation of tropical polytopes. OSCAR, with polymake within it, does not yet have a tropical polytope type that represents the mathematical object in its full generality. To be able to include tropical polytopes in tropical projective space $\mathbb{TP}^{(d-1)}$ (the compactification of $\mathbb{TA}^{(d-1)}$), we have to deal with the decomposition of the boundary. These boundary decompositions are formalized as *strata* in section 5.1 of [Jos21].

References

- [AAGH20] Xavier Allamigeon, Abdellah Aznag, Stéphane Gaubert, and Yassine Hamdi, *The tropicalization of the entropic barrier*, 2020.
- [ABGJ14a] Xavier Allamigeon, Pascal Benchimol, Stéphane Gaubert, and Michael Joswig, *Combinatorial simplex algorithms can solve mean payoff games*, *SIAM J. Optim.* **24** (2014), no. 4, 2096–2117. MR 3504692
- [ABGJ14b] Xavier Allamigeon, Pascal Benchimol, Stéphane Gaubert, and Michael Joswig, *Long and winding central paths*, *Recent Advances in Linear Optimization* (Champs sur marne, France), July 2014.
- [ABGJ15] Xavier Allamigeon, Pascal Benchimol, Stéphane Gaubert, and Michael Joswig, *Tropicalizing the simplex algorithm*, *SIAM J. Discrete Math.* **29** (2015), no. 2, 751–795. MR 3336300
- [ABGJ18] ———, *Log-barrier interior point methods are not strongly polynomial*, *SIAM J. Appl. Algebra Geom.* **2** (2018), no. 1, 140–178. MR 3772004
- [ABGJ21] ———, *What tropical geometry tells us about the complexity of linear programming*, *SIAM Rev.* **63** (2021), no. 1, 123–164. MR 4209657
- [AD09] Federico Ardila and Mike Develin, *Tropical hyperplane arrangements and oriented matroids*, *Math. Z.* **262** (2009), no. 4, 795–816. MR 2511751
- [ADS22] Ayah Almousa, Anton Dochtermann, and Ben Smith, *Root polytopes, tropical types, and toric edge ideals*, arXiv preprint arXiv:2209.09851 (2022).
- [AF24] Carlos Améndola and Kamillo Hugh Ferry, *Tropical combinatorics of weighted dag polyhedra*, "(preprint to appear)", 2024.
- [AGKS18] Xavier Allamigeon, Stéphane Gaubert, Ricardo D. Katz, and Mateusz Skomra, *Condition numbers of stochastic mean payoff games and what they say about nonarchimedean semidefinite programming*, 2018.
- [AGS18] Xavier Allamigeon, Stéphane Gaubert, and Mateusz Skomra, *Solving generic nonarchimedean semidefinite programs using stochastic game algorithms*, *J. Symbolic Comput.* **85** (2018), 25–54. MR 3707850
- [AGS20] ———, *Tropical spectrahedra*, *Discrete Comput. Geom.* **63** (2020), no. 3, 507–548. MR 4074332
- [AGV22] Xavier Allamigeon, Stéphane Gaubert, and Nicolas Vandame, *No self-concordant barrier interior point method is strongly polynomial*, *STOC '22—Proceedings of the 54th Annual ACM SIGACT Symposium on Theory of Computing*, ACM, New York, [2022] ©2022, pp. 515–528. MR 4490019
- [AMO93] Ravindra K. Ahuja, Thomas L. Magnanti, and James B. Orlin, *Network flows: Theory, algorithms, and applications*, 1993.

- [BA09] P. Butkovic and A. Aminu, *Introduction to max-linear programming*, IMA J. Manag. Math. **20** (2009), no. 3, 233–249. MR 2511497
- [Ben14] Pascal Benchimol, *Tropical aspects of linear programming*, Theses, Ecole Polytechnique, December 2014.
- [BLM22a] Enrico Bortoletto, Niels Lindner, and Berenike Masing, *The tropical and zonotopal geometry of periodic timetables*, Tech. Report 22-09, ZIB, Takustr. 7, 14195 Berlin, 2022.
- [BLM22b] ———, *Tropical neighbourhood search: A new heuristic for periodic timetabling*, Algorithmic Approaches for Transportation Modeling, Optimization, and Systems, 2022.
- [BPT13] Grigoriy Blekherman, Pablo A. Parrilo, and Rekha R. Thomas (eds.), *Semidefinite optimization and convex algebraic geometry*, MOS-SIAM Series on Optimization, vol. 13, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM), Philadelphia, PA; Mathematical Optimization Society, Philadelphia, PA, 2013. MR 3075433
- [CC23] Shelby Cox and Mark Curiel, *The tropical polytope is the set of all weighted tropical fermat-weber points*, 2023.
- [CGQ04] Guy Cohen, Stéphane Gaubert, and Jean-Pierre Quadrat, *Duality and separation theorems in idempotent semimodules*, vol. 379, 2004, Tenth Conference of the International Linear Algebra Society, pp. 395–422. MR 2039751
- [CLY24] Marcel Celaya, Georg Loho, and Chi Ho Yuen, *Oriented matroids from triangulations of products of simplices*, Selecta Math. (N.S.) **30** (2024), no. 3, Paper No. 47, 32. MR 4739563
- [DEF⁺24] Wolfram Decker, Christian Eder, Claus Fieker, Max Horn, and Michael Joswig (eds.), *The Computer Algebra System OSCAR: Algorithms and Examples*, 1 ed., Algorithms and Computation in Mathematics, vol. 32, Springer, 8 2024.
- [DJS12] Anton Dochtermann, Michael Joswig, and Raman Sanyal, *Tropical types and associated cellular resolutions*, J. Algebra **356** (2012), 304–324. MR 2891135
- [DLRS10] Jesús De Loera, Jörg Rambau, and Francisco Santos, *Triangulations: structures for algorithms and applications*, vol. 25, Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [DS04] Mike Develin and Bernd Sturmfels, *Tropical convexity*, Doc. Math. **9** (2004), 1–27. MR 2054977
- [DY07] Mike Develin and Josephine Yu, *Tropical polytopes and cellular resolutions*, Experiment. Math. **16** (2007), no. 3, 277–291. MR 2367318
- [FO22] Dario Frascaria and Neil Olver, *Algorithms for flows over time with scheduling costs*, Math. Program. **192** (2022), no. 1-2, 177–206. MR 4391767

- [FR15] Alex Fink and Felipe Rincón, *Stiefel tropical linear spaces*, J. Combin. Theory Ser. A **135** (2015), 291–331. MR 3366480
- [GGP97] Israel M. Gelfand, Mark I. Graev, and Alexander Postnikov, *Combinatorics of hypergeometric functions associated with positive roots*, The Arnold-Gelfand mathematical seminars, Birkhäuser Boston, Boston, MA, 1997, pp. 205–221. MR 1429893
- [GJ00] Ewgenij Gawrilow and Michael Joswig, *polymake: a framework for analyzing convex polytopes*, pp. 43–73, Birkhäuser Basel, Basel, 2000.
- [Gr03] Branko Grünbaum, *Convex polytopes*, second ed., Graduate Texts in Mathematics, vol. 221, Springer-Verlag, New York, 2003, Prepared and with a preface by Volker Kaibel, Victor Klee and Günter M. Ziegler. MR 1976856
- [JK10] Michael Joswig and Katja Kulas, *Tropical and ordinary convexity combined*, Adv. Geom. **10** (2010), no. 2, 333–352. MR 2629819
- [JK15] Marianne Johnson and Mark Kambites, *Convexity of tropical polytopes*, Linear Algebra Appl. **485** (2015), 531–544. MR 3394163
- [JL16] Michael Joswig and Georg Loho, *Weighted digraphs and tropical cones*, Linear Algebra Appl. **501** (2016), 304–343. MR 3485070
- [JL20] ———, *Monomial tropical cones for multicriteria optimization*, SIAM J. Discrete Math. **34** (2020), no. 2, 1172–1191. MR 4101364
- [Jos05] Michael Joswig, *Tropical halfspaces*, Combinatorial and computational geometry, Math. Sci. Res. Inst. Publ., vol. 52, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 2005, pp. 409–431. MR 2178330
- [Jos21] ———, *Essentials of tropical combinatorics*, Graduate Studies in Mathematics, vol. 219, American Mathematical Society, Providence, RI, [2021] ©2021. MR 4423372
- [JSY07] Michael Joswig, Bernd Sturmfels, and Josephine Yu, *Affine buildings and tropical convexity*, Albanian J. Math. **1** (2007), no. 4, 187–211. MR 2367213
- [Kr05] Daniel Král, *An exact algorithm for the channel assignment problem*, Discrete Appl. Math. **145** (2005), no. 2, 326–331. MR 2113152
- [LMS01] G. L. Litvinov, V. P. Maslov, and G. B. Shpiz, *Idempotent functional analysis. An algebraic approach*, Mat. Zametki **69** (2001), no. 5, 758–797. MR 1846814
- [Loh20] Georg Loho, *Abstract tropical linear programming*, Electron. J. Combin. **27** (2020), no. 2, Paper No. 2.51, 68. MR 4245106
- [LP07] Thomas Lam and Alexander Postnikov, *Alcoved polytopes. I*, Discrete Comput. Geom. **38** (2007), no. 3, 453–478. MR 2352704

- [LP18] ———, *Alcoved polytopes II*, Lie groups, geometry, and representation theory, Progr. Math., vol. 326, Birkhäuser/Springer, Cham, 2018, pp. 253–272. MR 3890212
- [LS23] Georg Loho and Ben Smith, *Face posets of tropical polyhedra and monomial ideals*, Electron. J. Combin. **30** (2023), no. 4, Paper No. 4.11, 57. MR 4657284
- [LS24] Georg Loho and Mateusz Skomra, *Signed tropical halfspaces and convexity*, 2024.
- [LV20] Georg Loho and László A. Végh, *Signed tropical convexity*, 11th Innovations in Theoretical Computer Science Conference, LIPIcs. Leibniz Int. Proc. Inform., vol. 151, Schloss Dagstuhl. Leibniz-Zent. Inform., Wadern, 2020, pp. Art. No. 24, 35. MR 4048127
- [MS15] Diane Maclagan and Bernd Sturmfels, *Introduction to tropical geometry*, Graduate Studies in Mathematics, vol. 161, American Mathematical Society, Providence, RI, 2015. MR 3287221
- [OSC24] *Oscar – open source computer algebra research system, version 1.2.0-dev*, 2024.
- [RGST05] Jürgen Richter-Gebert, Bernd Sturmfels, and Thorsten Theobald, *First steps in tropical geometry*, Idempotent mathematics and mathematical physics, Contemp. Math., vol. 377, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2005, pp. 289–317. MR 2149011
- [San05] Francisco Santos, *The Cayley trick and triangulations of products of simplices*, Integer points in polyhedra—geometry, number theory, algebra, optimization, Contemp. Math., vol. 374, Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2005, pp. 151–177. MR 2134766
- [Sko18] Mateusz Skomra, *Spectraèdres tropicaux : application à la programmation semi-définie et aux jeux à paiement moyen*, Theses, Université Paris Saclay (COMUE), December 2018.
- [Spe08] David E. Speyer, *Tropical linear spaces*, SIAM J. Discrete Math. **22** (2008), no. 4, 1527–1558. MR 2448909
- [SS04] David Speyer and Bernd Sturmfels, *The tropical Grassmannian*, Adv. Geom. **4** (2004), no. 3, 389–411. MR 2071813
- [SU89] Paolo Serafini and Walter Ukovich, *A mathematical model for periodic scheduling problems*, SIAM J. Discrete Math. **2** (1989), no. 4, 550–581. MR 1018539
- [SW09] Yidong Sun and Zhiping Wang, *String pattern avoidance in generalized non-crossing trees*, Discrete Math. Theor. Comput. Sci. **11** (2009), no. 1, 79–93. MR 2513875
- [Tan] Till Tantau, *The tikz and pgf packages*.
- [Tra17] Ngoc Mai Tran, *Enumerating polytropes*, J. Combin. Theory Ser. A **151** (2017), 1–22. MR 3663485

- [ZLY24] Manru Zong, Yin Tat Lee, and Man-Chung Yue, *Short-step methods are not strongly polynomial-time*, Math. Program. **207** (2024), no. 1-2, 733–746. MR 4783209